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RIGOUROUS -

secuRe desIGn and depLOyment of trUsthwoRthy
cOntinUum computing 6G Services

Deliverable 3.3

**FINAL RESULTS OF THE MULTI-DOMAIN
AUTOMATED SECURITY ORCHESTRATION, TRUST
MANAGEMENT AND DEPLOYMENT**

Title	Deliverable D3.3 - Final results of the Multi-domain automated security orchestration, trust-management and deployment
Document description	This deliverable will report the final results of the multi-domain automated security orchestration, trust-management, and deployment. Furthermore, this deliverable will report the scientific outcomes from the four tasks as well as the implementation aspects of the related Trust manager, AI-driven orchestrator, End-to-End multi-domain Slice Manager and the Human-Centric DevSecOps tools respectively.
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Table of Contents

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
2 INTRODUCTION	8
2.1. BACKGROUND	8
2.2. OBJECTIVES	8
2.3. ORGANISATION OF THE DOCUMENT	9
3 HUMAN-CENTRIC SECURITY, PRIVACY MODELING AND ONBOARDING	9
3.1. SECURITY AND PRIVACY FORMAL DATA MODELS FOR 6G NETWORKS	9
3.1.1. SECURITY POLICY MODELS	9
3.1.2. COMMAND AND CONTROL POLICY	11
3.1.3. FEDERATED LEARNING	12
3.1.4. FIREWALL	14
3.1.5. SIEM POLICY	17
3.1.6. NETWORK SLICING	17
3.1.6.1. CREATE	17
3.1.6.1. ATTACH	18
3.1.7. MONITORING / IDS	19
3.2. SECURITY POLICY CONFLICT DETECTION	21
3.3. HUMAN-CENTRIC USER-FRIENDLY TOOLS FOR DEVSECOPS AND RISK MANAGEMENT	22
3.3.1. PRIVGUIDE	23
3.3.2. PRIVACY QUANTIFIER	25
3.4. ONBOARDING TOOLS	26
3.4.1. RISK SPECIFICATION	28
3.4.2. NFV SECURITY ONBOARDING SPECIFICATION	29
3.4.3. NETWORK-BASED MOVING TARGET DEFENSE (NMTD)	31
3.5. USER CONTROLLED VERIFIABLE SECURE DIGITAL IDENTIFICATION SERVICE	32
4 AI-DRIVEN CROSS-DOMAIN SECURITY AND PRIVACY ORCHESTRATION IN IOT-EDGE-CLOUD CONTINUUM	32
4.1. MULTI-DOMAIN AI-DRIVEN ORCHESTRATOR FOR IOT-EDGE-CLOUD CONTINUUM	32
4.1.1. SECURITY ORCHESTRATION ARCHITECTURE	32

4.1.2.	CONTROLLERS, DRIVERS, ENABLERS AND PLUGINS FOR SECURITY ORCHESTRATION	34
4.1.3.	END-TO-END SECURITY ORCHESTRATION	36
4.1.4.	AI-BASED ORCHESTRATION ALGORITHMS	37
4.2.	IOT BOOTSTRAPPING MECHANISMS	41
4.3	TRUSTED APPLICATION ONBOARDING	41
5	ZERO TRUST AND SMART SECURITY MANAGEMENT	42
5.1.	TRUST EVALUATION AND TRUST ENABLER SERVICE FRAMEWORK	42
5.2	TRUST ALGORITHM:	43
I.	MULTIMODAL DATA	43
II.	MODEL STRUCTURE	43
III.	LOSS FUNCTION	44
IV.	ANOMALY SCORE CALCULATION	44
V.	TRUST SCORE ASSIGNMENT	44
5.3	EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS	45
6	END-TO-END MULTIDOMAIN MULTI-TENANT 6G SLICING	47
6.1.	SECURITY AGENTS AND SECURITY SLICE CONTROLLERS FOR END-TO-END MULTI-DOMAIN SLICING	47
6.1.1.	ORCHESTRATION OF CHANNEL-PROTECTED SECURITY SLICES	47
6.1.2.	SLICE MANAGER	48
6.1.3.	NETWORK SELF-PROTECTION	50
7	WP3 ENABLERS SHOWCASING	55
7.1	USE CASE DESCRIPTION	55
7.2	WP3 ASSETS INVOLVED	57
7.2.1	SECURITY ORCHESTRATION	57
7.2.2	SLICING	57
7.2.3	FILTERING	58
7.2.4	IDS RECONFIGURATION	59
7.2.5	TRUST MANAGEMENT	59
7.2.6	ONBOARDING	60
8	CONCLUSION	61
7	LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS	61

10 LIST OF FIGURES	66
11 LIST OF TABLES	67
12 REFERENCES	67

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the final outcomes of research and implementation across four WP3 tasks, focusing on automated security orchestration, trust management, and policy-based and secure deployment in multi-domain 6G environments. It highlights the development of key components including the Trust Manager, AI-driven Orchestrator, End-to-End Slice Manager, and Human-Centric DevSecOps tools. In this D3.3 deliverable, unlike D3.2, the document includes the performance evaluation of the assets developed in the scope of WP3. The main outcomes are summarized below:

Task 3.1: Human-Centric Security, Privacy Modelling, and Onboarding

- Security and Privacy Models for 6G: A detailed system model is defined with four components (capacity, enablers, API, and software), illustrated via UML. Security policies in MSPL and OpenC2 languages are used to enforce infrastructure protections. A Federated Learning (FL) policy framework and integration with VyOS enhance security agent configuration and policy translation. Policy models have been updated and new ones have been included in D3.3 compared to D3.2. Conflict detection mechanisms in policies have been defined.
- Human-Centric DevSecOps and Risk Management Tools: A privacy modelling and quantification system supports dynamic privacy assessment using service-specific manifests. The Human-Controllable Privacy UI (PUI) enables user-driven privacy management. APIs support onboarding and risk analysis.
- Onboarding Tools: Built on OpenSlice, the onboarding process includes enhanced UI components for designing secure and privacy-aware VNFs. Key tools include the Service Composition UI, Application Onboarding UI, and enhanced NFV Catalog. Integration with TM Forum APIs and Moving Target Defense (MTD) techniques ensures resilient and adaptive network services.
- Decentralized Identification and Trust Management: A decentralized identity service based on ETSI PDL standards enables secure digital identities and trusted interactions using Permissioned Distributed Ledger (PDL) technologies. It supports DID registration, access control, and selective data exposure. This asset has not evolved since D3.2 so that the reader is referred to D3.2 for information.

Task 3.2: AI-Driven Cross-Domain Orchestration for IoT-Edge-Cloud

- AI-Based Security Orchestration: Enhancing the INSPIRE-5Gplus framework, an AI-driven orchestrator manages security across network segments (IoT, RAN, edge, core, cloud), enabling real-time deployment and reconfiguration of security functions. Policies are translated and enforced through a structured orchestration workflow.
- IoT Bootstrapping: Secure onboarding of IoT devices begins with default credentials and transitions to Attribute-Based Verifiable Credentials, allowing trusted access to services and device-to-device communication. This asset has not evolved since D3.2 so that the reader is referred to D3.2 for further information.

- **Trusted Application Onboarding:** Applications disclose data handling practices to enable deployment choices based on privacy levels. A credential system verifies developers and ensures only certified applications are onboarded securely. This asset has not evolved since D3.2 so that the reader is referred to D3.2 for further information.

Task 3.3: Zero Trust and Smart Security Management

- **Trust Evaluation Framework (TESF):** TESF assigns trust scores based on behaviour deviations and security metrics from various network components. It supports timely, automated responses through an AI decision engine. The deliverable details TESF architecture, supported technologies, and final test results with additional trust evaluation conditions.

Task 3.4: End-to-End Multi-Domain 6G Slicing

- **Secure Slicing Architecture:** Security agents and slice controllers collaborate to monitor, manage, and enforce security policies across slices. Agents collect real-time data, while controllers execute orchestrator-directed policies for robust slice protection.
- **End-to-End multidomain and multi-operator channel protection** through policy-based and automatic IPsec tunnels. This deliverable describes the approach and evaluation conducted.

Each section in the document includes final implementations and results based on current development stages. The document includes at the end a section intended to showcase and evaluate the integration of different WP3 assets to counter attacks in B5G networks.

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1. Background

Deliverable D3.3 describes the final outcomes of the RIGOUROUS project of WP3. The document focuses on the final results of the multi-domain automated security orchestration, trust management, and security deployment with different security enablers. It covers the implementation and evaluation of various key solutions specific to the WP3 tasks, such as:

- Human-Centric security, privacy modelling, and onboarding
- AI-driven cross-domain Security and Privacy orchestration in IoT-edge-cloud continuum
- Zero trust and Smart security management
- End-to-End multi-domain multi-tenant 6G slicing.

The report details scientific outcomes of the four tasks and provides detailed insights into the implementation aspects of the Trust manager, AI-driven orchestrator, End-to-End multi-domain Slice Manager, and Human-Centric DevSecOps tools.

The document also features a section intended to showcase the integration of WP3 assets to mitigate attacks by enforcing by the orchestrator different countermeasures, like IDS reconfiguration, Slicing attacker, filtering network traffic, recalculate trust and reconfigure the onboarding tools,

2.2. Objectives

The objectives of this deliverable align with those of Work Package 3 (WP3) and the broader goals of the project, particularly:

- Objective 1: A holistic smart service framework for securing the IoT-Edge-Cloud continuum throughout its lifecycle management,
- Objective 2: Human-centric DevSecOps, and
- Objective 3: Model-based and AI-driven automated security orchestration, trust management, and deployment.

Specifically, this deliverable aims to:

- For Objective 1: Building on the outcomes of D2.1 "System Requirements Analysis Report", it further develops the framework's functional architecture by detailing the multi-domain orchestration architecture.
- For Objective 2: It presents the design and prototyping of human-centric tools for security, privacy modelling, and onboarding.
- For Objective 3: It details the design and prototyping of AI-driven orchestration, zero-trust security management, and end-to-end multi-domain network slicing.

2.3. Organisation of the document

The rest of the document is structured as follows. Section 3 presents the human-centric security, privacy modeling and onboarding aspects; tools for DevSecOps, risk management, onboarding; and enablers for secure digital identification service. Section 4 details the AI driven cross-domain security and privacy orchestration aspect for IoT-edge-cloud continuum and Section 5 elaborates the Zero trust and smart security management. Further, Section 6 describes the End-to-End multidomain multi-tenant 6G slicing aspects. Then, Section 7 showcases the integration of WP3 assets to orchestrate countermeasures to mitigate an attack in a complex use-case. Finally, section 8 concludes the deliverable.

3 HUMAN-CENTRIC SECURITY, PRIVACY MODELING AND ONBOARDING

3.1. Security and Privacy formal data models for 6G networks

3.1.1. Security policy models

The security policy models allow the Security Orchestrator (through the use of the Intent-based Security Manager) to process MSPL policies that provide necessary security measures for the RIGOUROUS infrastructure, such as the security slicing policies, which allow traffic integrity and encryption in network slices using IPsec. With the integration of these models, the Security Orchestrator is able to generate and send IPsec configuration messages to Software-Defined Networking (SDN) controllers in the RIGOUROUS architecture, which will generate and distribute the configuration to the correspondent devices, allowing the creation of secure IPsec tunnels between the SDN-controlled devices. Our plan is to extend this behavior to also be able to secure traffic in multi-domain SDN environments. Other security policy models include filtering and firewall features, that also provide security measures to prevent and react to network attacks.

Figure 5 shows the definition of security policy models in the system model schema. We can see that the policy has a parameter named "spd", of type "SPD", that is defined in Figure 6, which represents a Security Policy Database (SPD) entry, a database that stores IPsec security policies that depict the traffic to be secured. We can see then that the SPD definition contains a pair of parameters for IP addresses ("localAddress" and "remoteAddress"), the IPsec protection mode (transport or tunnel), and the Security Association Database (SAD) entry, defined in Figure 7, which stores IPsec security associations, that contain the algorithms and keys to use to secure traffic. There, we can see that the SAD is composed of the parameters needed for packet security: "encryptionAlgorithm" and "integrityAlgorithm" contain algorithms for encryption and integrity, "encryptionKey" and "integrityKey" contain the shared secret used to secure the messages (there are two instances of each one, as in bidirectional communication two pairs of different shared secrets are used to create SAs (Security Associations): one for incoming traffic, and another for outgoing traffic), "enclv" contains an initialization vector, a random string that some algorithms need to add more randomness to the encryption process, and lastly two sets of parameters, one starting with the prefix "soft" ("softByte", "softPackets", "softAdded" and "softUsed"), and

another starting with "hard" ("hardByte", "hardPackets", "hardAdded" and "hardUsed"). Both sets represent the lifetime for the IPsec SAs, but each one has a different meaning. The "soft" lifetimes indicate when the SA needs to be renewed (in a process named rekey), but it is still valid until the "hard" lifetime is reached. After the "hard" lifetime moment, the SA is removed from the device, so it should have been renewed before to avoid traffic loss between the devices.

```
<complexType name="SecurityConfigurationCondition">
  <complexContent>
    <extension base="ITResource:ParametersSecurityConfigurationCondition"> </extension>
  </complexContent>
</complexType>

<complexType name="ParametersSecurityConfigurationCondition">
  <complexContent>
    <extension base="ITResource:ConfigurationCondition">
      <sequence>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="spd"
          type="ITResource:SPD"/>
      </sequence>
    </extension>
  </complexContent>
</complexType>
```

Figure 1 - Security Policy models definition in System Model schema

```
<complexType name="SPD">
  <complexContent>
    <extension base="ITResource:ConfigurationCondition">
      <sequence>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="1" name="localAddress" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="1" name="remoteAddress" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="1" name="modeType" type="ITResource:SecureModeType"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="sad" type="ITResource:SAD"/>
      </sequence>
    </extension>
  </complexContent>
</complexType>
```

Figure 2 - SPD definition for Security Policy in System Model schema

```
<complexType name="SAD">
  <complexContent>
    <extension base="ITResource:ConfigurationCondition">
      <sequence>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="encryptionAlgorithm" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="2" minOccurs="0" name="encryptionKey" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="encIv" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="integrityAlgorithm" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="2" minOccurs="0" name="intKey" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="softByte" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="softPackets" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="softAdded" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="softUsed" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="hardByte" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="hardPackets" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="hardAdded" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="hardUsed" type="string"/>
      </sequence>
    </extension>
  </complexContent>
</complexType>
```

Figure 3 - SAD definition for Security Policy in System Model schema

3.1.2. Command and control policy

To operate the camera, we are using OASIS OpenC2. OpenC2 is a standardized language used for command and control of cyber defense technologies. It facilitates the coordination and automation of defense actions across different systems. In the context of managing a camera, OpenC2 commands could be used to direct the camera's operations, such as turning it on or off, changing its settings, or capturing images, all through a common, machine-readable format that ensures interoperability between different security devices and platforms.

Figure 8 shows the most important part of the schema declaration for creating command and control policies, in this case to control a camera.

```
<complexType name="CommandControlRuleAction">
  <complexContent>
    <extension base="ITResource:ConfigurationAction">
      <sequence>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="commandControlActionType" type="ITResource:CommandControlActionType"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="ruleParameters" type="ITResource:CommandControlConfigurattionCondition"/>
      </sequence>
    </extension>
  </complexContent>
</complexType>
```

Figure 4 - CommandControlRuleAction definition for Command and Control in System Model schema

As we can see in Figure 9, as for the type of command and control we only declare CAMERA, this can be extended for future contributions.

```
<simpleType name="CommandControlActionType">
  <restriction base="string">
    <enumeration value="CAMERA"/>
  </restriction>
</simpleType>
```

Figure 5 - CommandControlActionType definition for Command and Control in System Model schema

Based on this, the main elements of camera operation using OpenC2 are shown in Figure 10. These elements are request, response, action, device_id, driver_device_id and command_id. The request and response elements provide a way to determine if the OpenC2 message corresponds with a request from the Security Orchestrator to the camera, or a response from the camera to the Security Orchestrator. The action element contains the action to enforce in the camera (which for the Mobitrust use case, the available values are "stoprecording" and "stopstreaming", to stop the camera recording or streaming, respectively). Lastly, the device_id and driver_device_id identify the target camera and the driver it's running.

```
<complexType name="CameraRuleParameters">
  <complexContent>
    <extension base="ITResource:ConfigurationCondition">
      <sequence>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="request" type="boolean"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="response" type="boolean"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="action" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="macAddress" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="command_id" type="string"/>
      </sequence>
    </extension>
  </complexContent>
</complexType>
```

Figure 6 - CameraRuleParameters definition for Command and Control in System Model schema

3.1.3. Federated Learning

To establish and configure the requisite elements for FL within the infrastructure as Security Agents, an interoperable and inventive FL policy framework was devised, encapsulating all critical details. The FL configuration policy, in conjunction with the plugin and driver implemented in the orchestrator, detailed in D3.1 allows the deployment of both FL agents and FL aggregators dynamically and on-demand (based on the needs), so a new detection model, updated with the current status of the network, can be trained by means of FL to replace the existing model in the detection engine, without having to stop the detection process for this purpose.

The FilterFLConfigurationCondition groups all key parameters required to configure a Federated Learning setup. instanceThreshold sets the minimum number of client instances needed to start training; aggregatorParameters defines how the aggregator coordinates learning rounds; localConnectionParameters handles network or endpoint details for clients; integrationFabricParameters relates to the system that connects different components; learningModelInfo contains metadata about the model; learningParameters defines local training settings like epochs or batch size; and obfuscationInfo specifies how data or model updates are protected for privacy.

```
<complexType name="FilterFLConfigurationCondition">
  <complexContent>
    <extension base="ITResource:ConfigurationCondition">
      <sequence>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="instanceThreshold" type="integer" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="aggregatorParameters" type="ITResource:AggregatorParameters" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="localConnectionParameters" type="ITResource:LocalConnectionParameters" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="integrationFabricParameters" type="ITResource:IntegrationFabricParameters" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="learningModelInfo" type="ITResource:LearningModelInfo" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="learningParameters" type="ITResource:LearningParameters" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="obfuscationInfo" type="ITResource:ObfuscationInfo" />
      </sequence>
    </extension>
  </complexContent>
</complexType>
```

Figure 7 - FilterFLConfigurationCondition definition for Federated Learning in System Model schema

The AggregatorParameters shown in Figure 12, define settings for the aggregator in a Federated Learning system. URL specifies where the aggregator service is hosted, rounds sets how many global training iterations will occur, fusionAlgorithm indicates the method used to combine client models, apiPort defines the network port for API communication, and minClients sets the minimum number of clients required to participate in each round for aggregation to proceed.

```
<complexType name="AggregatorParameters">
  <complexContent>
    <extension base="ITResource:ConfigurationCondition">
      <sequence>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="URL" type="string" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="rounds" type="integer" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="fusionAlgorithm" type="string" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="apiPort" type="string" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="minClients" type="string" />
      </sequence>
    </extension>
  </complexContent>
</complexType>
```

Figure 8 - AggregatorParameters definition for Federated Learning in System Model schema

The LearningParameters in Figure 13, define local training settings for each client in a Federated Learning environment. testSize specifies the portion of data reserved for testing, localEpochs sets how many times the local dataset is used to train the model per round, batchSize defines the number of samples processed before the model is updated, and stepsPerEpoch indicates how many batches are run per epoch during local training.

```
<complexType name="LearningParameters">
  <complexContent>
    <extension base="ITResource:ConfigurationCondition">
      <sequence>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="testSize" type="string" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="localEpochs" type="string" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="batchSize" type="string" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="stepsPerEpoch" type="string" />
      </sequence>
    </extension>
  </complexContent>
</complexType>
```

Figure 9 - LearningParameters definition for Federated Learning in System Model schema

3.1.4. Firewall

With the aim to provide security to the RIGOROUS infrastructure, a new enabler is developed, which makes reference to a virtual firewall and is integrated like all other enablers. We have chosen VyOS as our open-source firewall solution [2]. VyOS is based on Debian and offers great flexibility. One of its key strengths is its ability to be deployed rapidly using Docker and Kubernetes, enabling dynamic deployment when needed.

First of all, we generate a policy to configure the firewall to drop messages from a specific IP address. Following the setup of the post request, we proceed to develop a translator capable of

parsing the input policy received from our orchestrator and converting it into an output in JSON format containing the main configuration parameters required by VyOS. This translator acts as a crucial intermediary component in our deployment pipeline, as it enables seamless communication between the input policy format, which may vary depending on our internal conventions or the requirements of other systems, and the specific configuration format expected by VyOS.

By implementing this translator, we ensure that the input policy is accurately interpreted and translated into a format that VyOS can readily understand and apply. This includes mapping policy elements such as firewall rules, network settings, and security configurations to their corresponding parameters in the VyOS configuration schema. Additionally, the translator may perform validation and normalization tasks to ensure that the generated configuration adheres to VyOS's syntax and constraints, thereby minimizing the risk of configuration errors or inconsistencies.

Once the translation process is complete, the output JSON containing the configured parameters is ready to be included in the post request payload sent to VyOS via curl. This seamless integration of translation and deployment processes enables efficient and reliable configuration management, facilitating the automation of network provisioning and ensuring consistency across our infrastructure.

Finally we finish shaping the post that sends the configuration to VyOS using the curl tool, this is done inside our orchestrator.

Figure 10 - Lifecycle of the filtering policy in the orchestrator

In Figure 14 we can see the main flow that the policy undergoes from the moment it enters our orchestrator until it leaves it. Passing through the translator and driver components. First of all,

there is the policy defined for the firewall, which once passed through the translator creates the necessary configuration for a firewall. From there it goes to the driver where this configuration is used to format it to the format understood by the VYOS API.

This is a basic policy of Firewall, where we aim to have the capacity to DROP and FORWARD packets. For this, we declare these two elements, that can be seen in Figure 15.

```
<complexType name="FirewallRuleAction">
  <complexContent>
    <extension base="ITResource:ConfigurationAction">
      <sequence>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="firewallActionType" type="ITResource:FirewallActionType" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="ruleParameters" type="ITResource:FirewallConfigurationCondition" />
      </sequence>
    </extension>
  </complexContent>
</complexType>
```

Figure 11- FirewallRuleAction definition for VyOS firewall in System Model schema

The first element was used to describe the type of policy that we need to define. This helps us in the process of translating this policy. We have two main types which are DROP and FORWARD, as shown in Figure 16.

```
<simpleType name="FirewallActionType">
  <restriction base="string">
    <enumeration value="DROP" />
    <enumeration value="FORWARD" />
  </restriction>
</simpleType>
```

Figure 12 - FirewallActionType definition for VyOS firewall in System Model schema

The main parameters that we need to configure the firewall are as follows, destinationAddress, action, sourceAddress and name, as depicted in Figure 17.

```
<complexType name="RuleParameters">
  <complexContent>
    <extension base="ITResource:ConfigurationCondition">
      <sequence>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="destinationAddress" type="string" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="action" type="string" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="sourceAddress" type="string" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="name" type="string" />
      </sequence>
    </extension>
  </complexContent>
</complexType>
```

Figure 13 - RuleParameters definition for VyOS firewall in System Model schema

The firewall policy can be useful in many use cases, for example to block malicious IPs quickly. For example, when the TRA detects an attack through an IP, it may need to filter the traffic coming from that IP.

3.1.5. SIEM policy

This policy defines an alert correlation configuration for Wazuh [13], aimed at detecting ‘ping of death’ attacks through Snort reported events. The policy configures Wazuh to correlate Snort events and identify a possible attack. If 5 events are detected within 60 seconds with a specific signature (sid 20101), Wazuh generates a level 10 alert.

The first important field is the capability statement “Network Traffic Analysis”. Then it defines a set of rules associated with the Snort agent. This rule reads: Events with rule ID 20101 (corresponding to an event in Snort) shall be observed. If 5 or more of these events are detected within 60 seconds, then an alert will be generated in Wazuh with level 10.

```
<rule>
  <id>222222</id>
  <level>10</level>
  <frequency>5</frequency>
  <timeframe>60</timeframe>
  <if_matched_sids>
    <if_matched_sid>20101</if_matched_sid>
  </if_matched_sids>
  <description>Wazuh example!</description>
</rule>
```

Figure 14 - SIEM rule example definition

3.1.6. Network slicing

This type of policy is applied in the RIGOUROUS framework to mitigate DDoS attacks by leveraging network slicing. It dynamically isolates and limits the bandwidth of the channels associated with each identified attacker, preserving overall Quality of Service (QoS) for legitimate traffic.

3.1.6.1. Create

This MSPL policy defines the creation of a network slice under Network Slicing capability, for DDoS attacks this is done through Software Defined Networking (SDN) to isolate and prioritise traffic

with specific Quality of Service (QoS) guarantees. The capability defined in the sysmodel is used within the policy.

```
<configurationRuleAction xsi:type="NetworkSlicingAction">
  <NetworkSlicingActionType>CREATE</NetworkSlicingActionType>
</configurationRuleAction>
```

Figure 15- Network Slicing Action Type

Within the network slicing policies, this one has a CREATE action, in charge of creating the slice.

```
<qosCondition>
  <isCNF>false</isCNF>
  <priority>1</priority>
  <maxBandwidth>10000000</maxBandwidth>
  <minBandwidth>1000000</minBandwidth>
</qosCondition>
```

Figure 16- QoS Condition

This part of the policy defines the quality of service of the slice. First, it sets the priority to 1 and sets the maximum bandwidth to 10Mbps and the minimum guaranteed bandwidth to 1Mbps.

```
<networkSlicingConditionParameters>
  <isCNF>false</isCNF>
  <SliceName>FLOW_SAMPLE_DO_SLICING1.sql</SliceName>
  <point>
    <isCNF>false</isCNF>
    <dpid>05DAB551</dpid>
    <dpid>05DAB551</dpid>
  </point>
  <SliceLocation>FE9B4176-14A9EFCC</SliceLocation>
</networkSlicingConditionParameters>
```

Figure 17- Slicing condition

This part of the policy starts by naming a network slice called FLOW_SAMPLE_DO_SLICING1.sql, associated to the network device identified by dpid 05DAB551, and located in the node or domain identified as FE9B4176-14A9EFCC.

3.1.6.1. Attach

This MSPL policy defines an ATTACH action within the Network Slicing capability, which means that it associates a specific network flow to an existing slice, identified by #sliceID and #sliceName. Like CREATE this policy uses the capability network_slicing.

```
<configurationRuleAction xsi:type="NetworkSlicingAction">
  <NetworkSlicingActionType>ATTACH</NetworkSlicingActionType>
</configurationRuleAction>
```

Figure 18 Network slicing Action

The type of action carried out in this policy is ATTACH.

```
<packetFilterCondition>
  <SourceMAC>40:00:00:06:00:01</SourceMAC>
  <DestinationMAC>40:00:00:06:00:01</DestinationMAC>
  <SourceAddress>00001010000001100000000000000010</SourceAddress>
  <DestinationAddress>0000101000000110000000000000010100</DestinationAddress>
  <direction>INGRESS</direction>
  <Interface>BD2F251B</Interface>
  <State>DROPPED</State>
  <innerPacket>
    <SourceAddress>10101100000101001101111000000011</SourceAddress>
    <DestinationAddress>10101100000101001101111011111110</DestinationAddress>
    <SourcePort>10000</SourcePort>
    <DestinationPort>80</DestinationPort>
    <ProtocolType>17</ProtocolType>
    <encapsulationType>gtp</encapsulationType>
    <encapsulationID>00000003</encapsulationID>
  </innerPacket>
</packetFilterCondition>
```

Figure 19-Packet filtering condition example

The filtering condition specifies that the target traffic must have both source and destination MAC address 40:00:00:00:06:00:00:01, with source IP 10.6.0.2 and destination IP 10.6.0.20, both in binary format. This traffic must come in on the BD2F251B interface and have a status marked DROPPED, which could indicate that it will be discarded if it is not associated with a slice. In addition, it includes an internal packet encapsulated in GTP (ID 3), with source IP address 172.84.222.3 and destination 172.84.222.254, using source port 10000, destination port 80, and UDP protocol (code 17).

```
<networkSlicingConditionParameters>
  <isCNF>false</isCNF>
  <SliceID>#sliceID</SliceID>
  <SliceName>#sliceName</SliceName>
  <SliceLocation>FE9B4176-14A9EFCC</SliceLocation>
</networkSlicingConditionParameters>
```

Figure 20- Network Slicing Condition parameters

This part is in charge of managing and identifying the CREATE to which each ATTACH is to be associated.

3.1.7. Monitoring / IDS

This MSPL policy belongs to the Network Traffic Analysis capability and is designed to trigger an alert when specific suspicious network traffic is detected. The rule targets ICMP Echo Request packets (Type 8).

The action to be taken under this policy is stated in the following part:

```
<configurationRuleAction xsi:type='MonitoringAction' >
  <monitoringActionType>ALERT</monitoringActionType>
</configurationRuleAction>
```

Figure 21 - Monitoring policy action example

These are the main parameters within the policy:

```
<packetFilterCondition>
  <DestinationAddress>8.8.8.8</DestinationAddress>
  <Size>>1500</Size>
  <ProtocolType>1</ProtocolType>
</packetFilterCondition>
<ICMPCondition>
  <Type>8</Type>
</ICMPCondition>
```

Figure 22 - Packet Filtering condition for IDS policy

The defined action is of type ALERT, which means that if such traffic is observed, the system will generate a security alert. The policy is intended to be enforced by a snort_agent, which is a signature-based intrusion detection system (IDS).

This configuration is especially useful for detecting anomalies such as Ping of Death attacks, where large ICMP packets are used to disrupt or crash remote systems. By filtering large ICMP echo requests to an external target such as 8.8.8.8, the policy enables proactive detection of potential network-level denial of service (DoS) activities. For example, in an enterprise network where multiple internal devices start sending unusually frequent ICMP Echo Request (ping) packets to an external IP address such as 8.8.8.8. By deploying this policy through the Snort agent, the system can detect and generate alerts for this suspicious behaviour, which may indicate a Ping of Death or an ICMP flood attack. This allows the security orchestrator or monitoring systems to take timely action, such as investigating compromised hosts or triggering mitigation measures to prevent a potential network-wide (DoS).

3.1.8. Metaorchestrator

We will now show how to put several types of policies into one policy.

```
<?xml version='1.0' encoding='UTF-8' standalone='yes'?>
<ITResourceOrchestration id="omsp1_9f1a88b4fc67421b98de270d5a63d311"
xmlns="http://modeliosoft/xsddesigner/a22bd60b-ee3d-425c-8618-beb6a854051a/ITResource.xsd"
xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"
xsi:schemaLocation="http://modeliosoft/xsddesigner/a22bd60b-ee3d-425c-8618-beb6a854051a/ITResource.xsd/ANASTACIA_MSPL_XML_Schema.xsd">
<ITResource id="mspl_9f1a88b4fc67421b98de270d5a63d36a" orchestrationID="omsp1_9f1a88b4fc67421b98de270d5a63d311">
<ITResource id="mspl_9f1a88b4fc67421b98de270d5a63d36b" orchestrationID="omsp1_9f1a88b4fc67421b98de270d5a63d311">
<ITResource id="mspl_9f1a88b4fc67421b98de270d5a63d36f" orchestrationID="omsp1_9f1a88b4fc67421b98de270d5a63d311">
</ITResourceOrchestration>
```

Figure 23 - Orchestration Policy example

These policies must be orchestrated according to parameters within the policy. An example could be priority.

```
<externalData xsi:type="Priority">
  <value>60000</value>
</externalData>
```

Figure 24- Priority in policies during orchestration

3.2. Security Policy conflict detection

When applying multiple security policies across the system architecture, it is crucial to avoid misconfigurations or conflicts that could affect service integrity. To address this, the Security Orchestrator integrates a lightweight conflict detection module that leverages an inference engine built with Pyke (Python Knowledge Engine). This component evaluates upcoming policy deployments against existing configurations, ensuring consistency and preventing the enforcement of contradictory rules. It also validates that each rule uses a unique identifier and blocks any new policy that could disrupt critical or high-priority services already in place.

As part of the orchestration process, it is necessary to anticipate and resolve both logical and operational incompatibilities before any security rule is enforced on elements such as SDN controllers or Virtual Security Functions (VSFs). These discrepancies may stem from conflicting configurations within a single orchestration flow or between multiple concurrent policies. The inference engine handles these scenarios through a rule-based reasoning approach that identifies and flags various types of semantic and contextual issues, including:

- Duplicate Behaviour Conflicts: Conflicts may arise if two different MSPL instances attempt to implement the same functional behaviour over the same network parameters for example, enforcing identical filtering rules at layer 4. This situation might occur if multiple administrators respond simultaneously to the same threat by independently applying similar countermeasures. The system detects the overlap and prevents redundant policy application.
- Execution Order Conflicts: Some security rules require strict execution sequences. A common issue occurs when a dependent policy is assigned a lower priority but is scheduled to run before its prerequisite. For instance, traffic filtering should follow the shutdown of

an IoT device, not precede it. The orchestrator identifies such inconsistencies in the enforcement order and alerts the administrator.

- **Capability Interference Conflicts:** A rule designed to perform one task might unintentionally block or degrade another. For example, deploying encrypted communication between endpoints can interfere with traffic monitoring mechanisms like DPI. If both configurations are active simultaneously on the same path, the orchestrator detects and reports the functional incompatibility.
- **Temporal and Logical Dependencies:** Certain policies are only valid when specific conditions have been met either the successful application of another policy or the occurrence of a specific event. A typical scenario involves requiring authentication to complete before applying authorization rules. The engine tracks such dependencies and blocks premature enforcement.
- **Contradictory Administrator Actions:** In environments with multiple administrators, it's possible for decisions to conflict over time or across roles. One policy may allow certain traffic while another blocks it. If this contradiction is detected either within the same policy batch or from previous deployments the orchestrator flags the inconsistency and prompts resolution.
- **Overlapping Rules with Different Strictness:** Sometimes a newly enforced policy might unintentionally relax constraints previously defined by a stricter rule. For instance, a policy allowing all traffic from a device could override a previous rule that permitted only specific protocols like CoAP. These situations are recognized as override conflicts.
- **Beyond these semantic checks,** the orchestrator also performs context-aware validations, which take the current infrastructure capabilities into account.
- **Missing Capability Conflicts:** A policy may require that a particular function such as DTLS-based channel protection be supported by the target node. If the device or virtualized function lacks that capability, the policy cannot be enforced. The conflict engine detects these gaps and prevents invalid deployments.

In addition, the orchestrator is capable of analyzing potential contradictions within a single policy goal, such as mismatches in the priorities assigned to individual policy components. By detecting these subtle issues early, the system avoids unintended behaviour and supports more reliable security automation across dynamic network environments.

3.3. Human-centric user-friendly tools for DevSecOps and risk management

DevPrivSecOps is a methodology that includes not only DevSecOps but also DevPrivOps into the DevOps pipeline, aiming to produce secure and privacy-aware software from its initial design stages. DevPrivOps, a paradigm that integrates development, privacy, and operations, necessitates a proactive approach to privacy evaluation and monitoring. Furthermore, one of the principles of DevPrivOps is to consider privacy-first measures into software design and engineering, instilling a culture of privacy by default, and aligning software development with emerging regulations and consumer expectations.

This need highlights the importance for a privacy guide to assist in implementing privacy measures aligned with the DevPrivOps paradigm. To address this problem, the logical next step is creating a design assistance tool to be integrated in the planning stage of DevPrivOps. As such, PrivGuide was developed. It takes the outputs of the selected Privacy Engineering Methodology (PEM), and design level information, providing privacy scores and indicators for the software, which can help identifying where it violates privacy design goals.

3.3.1. PrivGuide

PrivGuide is a tool that evaluates system descriptions according to user defined rules. The tool can be used by itself, all that is needed are the files for analysis (attack trees, system descriptions, regulations, requirements and schemas) and a triple store. By providing the tool with the files, it will analyse the descriptions and find privacy violations, possible attacks, impossible use cases and possible misuse cases. The analysis can happen in a CI/CD pipeline, ensuring a continuous DPIA and serving as a quality gate for the system architecture. The CI/CD pipeline deployment shown in Next figure demonstrates how a git server and CI/CD pipeline can communicate to deploy the tool in the pipeline and send the report to the report visualizer, that can live in another server.

Figure 25 - PrivGuide deployment diagram

The analysis produces a report in JSON format that contains a summary of all found issues. It also allows for visualization as any combination of clearance level and user group. To facilitate the creation and management of the files, we also provide a web interface (see Figure 26 - PrivGuide web interface.). This interface reads the tool's files and provides visual editors for all of them, visualization of descriptions based on plugins, and interface with the tool for analysis and testing.

Figure 26 - PrivGuide web interface.

PrivGuide has four components: the tool, the visualizer, the documentation and the web interface. We chose go as the language for the system, since it has a large presence in DevOps tooling and is an easy language to write and read, facilitating development and comprehension of the code. For the tool, we opted for a CLI, since it is the best interface to integrate on pipelines without sacrificing too much on local usage. To handle the interface, we opted for the cobra¹ package, as it is the most used and convenient command line parser available in the go ecosystem. To handle the JSON schema verification, we use go-yaml², the most used YAML parsing go library, and gojsonschema³, since it is the most complete JSON schema validator in the go ecosystem. We use Apache Jena Fuseki as a triple store, since it is open source and accepts queries and authentication through HTTP. The data is stored in a triple store as it is the most efficient and easy database paradigm to interact with to store arbitrary data over which complex relations need to be found. For the visualizer, we opted for the GOTTH stack, using go as the main language, templ⁴ as the templating engine, for its ease of writing and expressiveness compared to its alternatives, tailwindcss⁵ for styling, for its convenience and development speed, and htmx⁶ for a more ergonomic alternative to complex templates and client-side rendering in vanilla JavaScript, and finally the echo⁷ web framework for its simplicity, ease of use and broad adoption within the go ecosystem. The visualizer uses a single JSON file as a database, as adding an actual object database would add complexity to the deployment of this service and the volume of data transfers is not enough to make the inefficiency a problem in real world use. The documentation is a Zola website, so it would be easy to write, maintain and deploy while having an appealing interface. The web interface also uses the GOTTH stack for the same reasons as the visualizer, adding description visualization plugins in web assembly⁸.

¹ <https://github.com/spf13/cobra>

² <https://github.com/go-yaml/yaml>

³ <https://git.sr.ht/~emersion/go-jsonschema>

⁴ <https://github.com/a-h/templ>

⁵ <https://tailwindcss.com/>

⁶ <https://htmx.org/>

⁷ <https://echo.labstack.com/>

⁸ <https://webassembly.org/>

PrivGuide does not have any performance requirements, since it is used during design time and operates over very little data. However, it is still important to know that it does not consume more resources than reasonable. To evaluate the resource usage, we chose to measure how much time and memory the tool requires to process each of the demonstrative systems: **chat_app**, a basic chat application; **file_sharing**, a basic file sharing app; and **iot**, a very basic IoT home system. These measurements were taken by profiling the tool's resource usage with go's pprof⁹ tool, executing analysis over each system ten thousand times. All the tests were done in a laptop with an Intel Core i7-8750H CPU and 32GB of RAM, running arch linux with the 6.6.52-1-lts kernel.

Table 1 - Median and average execution time for the tool at 10000 executions

Application	Median time (ms)	Average time (ms)	Standard deviation (ms)
chat_app	302.7	300.9	80.03
file_sharing	302.4	299.7	79.99
iot	301.9	283.4	74.16

With regards to execution time, Table shows that the tool can analyse small systems in very little time.

Table 2 - Median and average memory usage for the tool at 10000 executions.

Application	Median memory usage (kb)	Average memory usage (kb)	Standard deviation (kb)
chat_app	1030.1	1214.3	434.78
file_sharing	1028.3	1138.8	353.04
iot	3088.3	2937.9	1052.5

With regards to memory, Table 2 - Median and average memory usage for the tool at 10000 executions. Table 2 shows that the tool can process the examples using a few mega bytes of memory, which is acceptable for usage in personal development machines and CI/CD pipelines.

3.3.2. Privacy Quantifier

The Privacy Quantifier (PQ) receives reports from the PrivGuide tool and generates a Privacy Manifest File (PMF) for the analysed application. From this report, the PQ identifies how data is handled and which Privacy Enhancing Technologies (PETs) are employed, using this information to produce a final privacy score. While this score is static — reflecting the analysis of the application at a given point in time — the PQ can also integrate with the Threat Risk Assessor (TRA) by combining the computed privacy score with risk information from the TRA, thereby providing a dynamic privacy view of the application.

⁹ <https://pkg.go.dev/runtime/pprof>

Currently, this integration is performed by passing the TRA information through a Python script that receives the Kafka messages from the TRA and calls a locally deployed ollama model, which calculates a numeric score based on the Common Vulnerability Scoring System (CVSS) from the TRA data. This score is appended to the risk score and CPE from the TRA message, which is then sent to the Onboarding Tools through an API request to update the score of the respective services.

3.4. Onboarding Tools

The Onboarding Tools comprise the OpenSlice Operations Support System (OSS), in addition to additional components that allow it to interact with the Security Orchestrator, for enforcement of the security and privacy policies described in Section 3.1, and the components pertaining to DevPrivSecOps and risk management detailed in Section 3.3. Next figure illustrates these components and the respective API endpoints used in their interaction.

Figure 27 - Components comprising the Onboarding Tools and their interaction

Specifically, via the Network-based Moving Target Defense (NMTD) component, the Onboarding Tools can send MSPL policies to the Security Orchestrator. As of the time of this deliverable, the supported policies are Firewall, SIEM, Telemetry, and Channel Protection (IPSec).

The interaction between OpenSlice and the NMTD can be done by leveraging the former's powerful Lifecycle Management (LCM) rules to make requests to the NMTD's API, namely its `/v2/os1` endpoint, specifically designed to receive the MSPL policies. After this, the NMTD will propagate the MSPL policies to the Security Orchestrator, awaiting its response and the respective configuration required to deploy the necessary services, according to the policies (Firewall, SIEM, etc.).

Following deliverable D3.2, a modification was made to the onboarding diagram in Figure 18 of D3.2, and the Application Onboarding UI (AOUI) was removed, no longer being included in the current version of the Onboarding Tools, as its function can be performed by OpenSlice's UI.

3.4.1. Risk Specification

A Risk Specification was defined to encapsulate the privacy and risk scores of services, which are computed by the PQ and the TRA, respectively. These scores are subsequently reflected in the services listed in the RIGOUROUS catalogue. Both the privacy score and the risk score are provided from the PQ as detailed in Section 3.3, and along with the CPE, are included in the Risk Specification in JSON format. This specification is consumed by the Onboarding Tools via the `/v2/risk` endpoint to dynamically update service scores. The remaining risk information about anomalies from the TRA can be optionally added to this specification, although the Onboarding Tools only requires the first three attributes present in Figure 3.4.1.1 (CPE, risk score and privacy score) to update the services.

```
{
  "cpe": string,
  "privacy_score": float,
  "risk_score": float,
  "anomalies": array
}
```

Figure 28 - Risk Specification.

After services are onboarded following natural OpenSlice onboarding flows, the services can be associated with different tags (Service Categories in the TM Forum ecosystem) and placed in the RIGOUROUS service catalogue. These tags can inform end users, for instance, about the privacy level of services and how their data is handled.

The DevPrivSecOps tools are capable of analysing services, assigning them different tags. To automatically receive these tags and associating to services in the RIGOUROUS catalogue, a simple REST API was developed, which assigns the received tags to a specified service. This is done by adding a Service Category with the same name as each tag received through the `/v2/tags/<service_id>` endpoint to the TM Forum Service Candidate corresponding to the service with ID `<service_id>`. Next figure shows these tags in the RIGOUROUS service catalogue.

Figure 29 - RIGOUROUS service catalogue with different tags related to privacy awareness

3.4.2. NFV Security Onboarding Specification

OpenSlice internally uses the TM Forum Service Specification to represent services. After onboarding the necessary NFV artifacts, service designers can define the characteristics of a service. These characteristics provide end users with important information about the service — for example, its IP address. In certain cases, characteristics can also be configured, enabling end users to customize services according to their preferences. Next figure illustrates a JSON representation of how the service port can be declared.

```
{
  "name": "Port",
  "serviceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": "80",
        "alias": ""
      }
    }
  ]
}
```

Figure 30 - Example of a TM Forum Service Specification Characteristic for declaring the port of a service

These service characteristics are also used to store the CPE, privacy score, and risk score of services, as introduced previously, along with all necessary information required to enforce policies received from the Security Orchestrator. This includes service MTD policies, which are represented using the TM Forum Service Specification in JSON format.

This type of policy enables the dynamic rotation of service characteristics, carried out by the Network-based Moving Target Defense (NMTD) enabler. To perform this rotation, the enabler requires information about which attributes to mutate, as well as how and when the rotation should occur. For each attribute to be mutated, an additional service characteristic is defined. This characteristic begins with the *Mutation::* prefix — similar to how primitives are implemented in OpenSlice¹⁰ — and includes the possible values the attribute can take, along with the rotation interval.

Although the TM Forum Service Specification allows characteristics to be constrained within a value range, this feature is not currently supported in OpenSlice. As a workaround, two new elements are added to the characteristic value, with the aliases *"valueFrom"* and *"valueTo"*, representing the minimum and maximum values (in minutes) for the interval, respectively. The rotation interval can either be selected at random within the specified range or explicitly set to the minimum or maximum value by declaring the *"interval"* attribute as *"random"*, *"min"*, or *"max"*. Next figure shows the JSON representation of this service characteristic.

```
{
  "name": "Mutation::Port",
  "serviceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": "min",
        "alias": "interval"
      },
      "value": {
        "value": "0",
        "alias": "valueFrom"
      },
      "value": {
        "value": "60",
        "alias": "valueTo"
      },
      "value": {
        "value": "[80, 8080, 10000-11000]",
        "alias": ""
      }
    }
  ]
}
```

¹⁰ https://osl.etsi.org/documentation/latest/service_design/nfv/design_nfv_services/#day-2-primitive-actions

Figure 31 - TM Forum Service Specification Characteristic for mutating the port of a service.

3.4.3. Network-based Moving Target Defense (NMTD)

The NMTD is a REST API that operates on top of OpenSlice, designed to deploy, modify, and terminate onboarded services given a TM Forum Service Specification. In addition, it includes an MTD component that enables the periodic rotation of service characteristics. The NMTD receives the specification of a service, including the desired service characteristics, via the `/v2/so` POST endpoint (this name was chosen as its main use case is to receive MTD policies from the Security Orchestrator). Figure 3.4.3.1 shows an example of a specific case of NMTD policies for rotating every attribute supported by a service.

```
{
  "name": "EMQX Broker",
  "serviceSpecCharacteristic": [
    {
      "name": "Mutation::All",
      "serviceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
        {
          "value": {
            "value": "min",
            "alias": "interval"
          }
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}
```

Figure 32 - NMTD policy in the TM Forum Service Specification format for rotation of all supported attributes

Technically, this enabler creates a TM Forum Service Order in OpenSlice using the provided Service Specification when deploying services. It also updates or terminates existing Service Orders as required. In addition, the service characteristics are updated accordingly.

The MTD component, internally referred to as the Rotation Manager, runs alongside the REST API and checks the existing Service Orders (i.e., running services) every minute for mutation characteristics (as discussed in the previous section). Identified characteristics are added to a queue of scheduled rotations based on the desired interval specified in the characteristics. If the time elapsed since a characteristic was last rotated exceeds the specified interval, the Rotation Manager updates the service's characteristics by selecting a new value from the predefined list of possible values (also defined within the characteristics).

Once the Service Order characteristics are updated in OpenSlice, it is possible to define Supervision LCM rules to propagate these changes to the underlying service implementations,

which is done anyway for Helm-based applications¹¹. Additionally, it is not limited to specific types of applications, as the NMTD can also work with regular VM-based services, since it does not distinguish between different underlying implementations — as long as an external component handles the necessary low-level mutations.

3.5. User controlled verifiable secure digital identification service

The user controlled verifiable secure digital identification service is described in detail in Deliverable D3.2, clause 3.4.

4 AI-DRIVEN CROSS-DOMAIN SECURITY AND PRIVACY ORCHESTRATION IN IoT-EDGE-CLOUD CONTINUUM

4.1. Multi-domain AI-driven Orchestrator for IoT-Edge-Cloud continuum

4.1.1. Security Orchestration architecture

The Security Orchestrator (SO) is in charge of the application of security policies to enablers in order to prevent or mitigate attacks. These policies are received from the Decision Engine component, which takes the decision to apply the most suitable policy depending on the event or anomaly detected in the RIGOUROUS architecture through the use of AI and machine learning techniques. The Security Orchestrator is able to analyse and process MSPL policies and create specific configuration messages to apply them in the corresponding enablers, thanks to the use of a set of components that provide different functionalities. Figure 4.1.1.1. shows the architectural design of the latest version of the SO prototype, including the communication with the following components:

- **System Model:** acts as a database that stores all the information related to the environment in which the SO is deployed, such as the capabilities that the SO supports, the enablers that can be managed and the endpoints that will be used to send the configurations.
- **Intent-based Security Management:** provides a way to process the MSPL policies received from the Decision Engine and create as a result a configuration message for the corresponding enabler.
- **Policy Repository:** stores the policies that are supported in the orchestrator.

¹¹ https://osl.etsi.org/documentation/latest/service_design/kubernetes/design_helm_aas/

- **Conflict Detector:** checks if the application of a new policy generates a problem with the previously deployed policies.
- **Allocation Manager:** in policies that involve the deployment of new components, it checks if there are enough resources in the environment to be allocated for them.

Following the flow of messages showed in Figure 4.1.1.1., we can see that the application of a MSPL policy starts from the Decision Engine, which determines the most suitable to apply in each situation. Then, the SO communicates with the System Model in order to ensure that it supports the capability required by the policy, that the enabler that will be the target of the policy has been already deployed in the environment, and to obtain the required information for the enforcement of the configuration in the enabler (for instance, the endpoint to send the configuration to). Next, the SO communicates with the Intent-based Security Manager to translate the MSPL policy into the correspondent configuration, which will also exchange messages with the Policy Repository to recover information about the supported policies in the SO. Internally, a dedicated plugin is used to obtain the required data from the MSPL and generate a configuration message, following the format and requisites for each enabler. Then, the Conflict Detector ensures that the application of a new policy do not interfere with the already deployed ones, by checking different elements such as the unique identification of each policy has not been duplicated. Following, if the policy involves the deployment of new components into the architecture (using a dedicated driver named NFV MANO), the SO needs to check if it is able to allocate the required resources to provide its functionality. Finally, the Security Orchestrator uses a specific driver to communicate with the enabler and send the configuration, which will be received by a Security Agent, and then applied in the enabler. Nevertheless, if the policy to apply involves the deployment of a new enabler or service, the NFV MANO driver is in charge of the deployment instead of a Security Agent.

Figure 33 - Security Orchestrator architecture diagram

4.1.2. Controllers, Drivers, Enablers and plugins for Security Orchestration

The Security Orchestration ecosystem comprises different internal components that helps the orchestrator to perform the required operations to transform MSPL policies into actual configurations in the enablers, as showed in Section 4.1.1. Most of these components are not usually depicted in figures regarding the architectural design around the orchestration process, even though they have a significant impact in the creation and application of the configuration. This section will cover with some more details how these components interact with the orchestrator and their purpose within the architecture.

Starting with the controllers, they are in charge of the management of other components in the architecture, mostly enablers. In this latest version of the Security Orchestrator prototype, there is only one type of controller: the Software-Defined Networking Controller (SDN controller), which is

part of the SDN architecture the SO manages for the deployment of channel protection policies. This type of controller acts as a higher level enabler and manages a set of components named SDN nodes, which are in charge of performing the operations to enforce IPsec-based channel protection tunnels. To achieve this, the SO sends a configuration message in JSON format to the correspondent SDN controller, including all the relevant information required to create the tunnel (source and destination IPs, encryption and integration algorithms, IVs, etc.), which will be used to create specific configuration messages in the SDN controller for each target SDN node that it manages. This way, the nodes only communicate to their controller in charge, and not directly with the SO.

Next, the drivers are another important part of the SO architecture that are not usually depicted, as they are in charge of the direct communication between the orchestrator and the enablers. As each enabler might have different ways to exchange messages with the controller, a new driver is always created when a new enabler needs to be configured, which also provides flexibility to modify or expand the implementation if needed. Most of them are based in direct communication through REST APIs via HTTP, using JSON as the message format, but other might use different types of communication or message format to adapt to the requirements of the enabler. Most of the drivers are used only for the configuration of enablers, but there is a special one that provides a way to create and deploy new enablers or services when a policy requires so: the NFV MANO driver. This driver uses virtualisation software, such as Docker or Kubernetes, to deploy directly VNF services or drivers in the architecture under demand.

An enabler is the generic way to design a component that provides a certain capability for the SO, which in most cases it needs to be configured or deployed. All the information regarding the capabilities supported, the enablers that have been deployed, and the endpoint to be configured is stored in the System Model, which the SO queries after receiving a policy to apply to perform some checks before start processing the policy. The list of the enablers that the SO currently is able to configure is:

- **Network Slice Manager:** provides a way to create and manage 5G network slices to mitigate some types of attacks (for instance, to reduce the bandwidth of a slice under a DDoS attack).
- **Channel Protection (SDN controller & SDN node):** creates and manages IPsec-based tunnels between enablers with integrity and encryption capabilities, which is useful to mitigate Man-In-The-Middle and other eavesdropping-related attacks.
- **Federated Learning (Agent & Aggregator):** agents are deployed in the network to obtain information about the network and detect anomalies through federated learning, while aggregators combine the knowledge obtained from the agents.
- **Firewall:** provide a way to deploy rules for virtual firewalls, to stop network communication to and from a component in the architecture.
- **Command & Control:** uses the generic OpenC2 interface for management of configurations.
- **Security Information & Event Management (SIEM):** this enabler records anomalies detected in the architecture and the network, and provides a way to manage the information related to them, such as create alerts or classify anomalies by criticality.

- **Telemetry:** it obtains and stores statistics from the network usage and data transmission.
- **Intrusion Detection System (IDS):** it detects and provides alerts, reporting anomalies in the environment to prevent the intrusion of external agents to assets in the architecture.

Finally, plugins provide a way to generate configuration messages from a policy. Similar to the drivers, they are created for each enabler and they allow extending the functionality to add or remove fields from the configuration. In most cases, they extract the required fields from the policies and create a configuration message following the desired format for the enabler (usually, JSON), but in some cases some more complex operations need to be performed in order to generate the required information.

4.1.3. End-to-End Security Orchestration

End-to-End Security Orchestration aims to provide a way to apply security policies in different parts of the network, that are managed by different Security Orchestrators. It involves the use of a higher-level Security Orchestrator, named End-to-End Security Orchestrator (E2E SO), with awareness of the different domains that manages, each one with also the presence of one (or more) Security Orchestrator. This high level orchestrator receives end-to-end MSPL security policies with information related to the enablers that need to be configured, the type of end-to-end policy to apply, and other orchestration-related data, such as the name for the rule, the domains affected, or the priority of application. The E2E SO will create individual MSPL messages for each SO in the target domains, containing all the information related to the configuration to apply in the correspondent enabler that the SO manages. Then, each SO will receive the policy and generate the actual configuration for the final enabler, thus applying the policy to the endpoints in each domain.

The End-to-End Security Orchestrator uses a similar architecture to the one showed in Section 4.1.1. for the Security Orchestrator, using a set of components that provide assistance during the process of end-to-end MSPL policies. Figure 4.1.3.1. depicts the connection between these components and the E2E SO, which are:

- **End-to-End System Model:** It stores all the information related to the environment where the E2E SO is deployed, including the domains it manages, the Security Orchestrators under these domains, and their endpoints to enforce end-to-end policies.
- **End-to-End Intent-based Security Manager:** This component is in charge of the translation of end-to-end MSPL policies into policies that are sent to the Security Orchestrators in charge of each domain. It communicates with the End-to-End Policy Repository component in order to obtain the set of available policies to apply.
- **End-to-End Policy Repository:** acts as a repository of end-to-end policies that are available to use for the Security Orchestrators to apply in their correspondent domains.
- **End-to-End Conflict Detector:** provides a simple way to check if a conflict exists between the already applied end-to-end policies before applying the new one.

- **End-to-End Allocation Manager:** this component is used only in policies that involve deploying new components in the architecture, as it is in charge of checking if the domains have enough resources to provide for the new component.

Figure 34 - End-to-End Security Orchestrator architecture diagram

4.1.4. AI-based orchestration algorithms

The AI-based meta-orchestration framework is proposed for multi-domain 6G deployments to manage VNF deployment and configuration. This last version of the Security Orchestrator includes the meta-orchestration process, as well as the use of AI algorithms to find the most suitable orchestration for each scenario. The meta-orchestration process involves three core phases (see Figure 4.1.4.1): first, selecting the most suitable orchestration strategy based on real-time policies and infrastructure constraints; second, constructing a deployment graph of feasible configuration

options; and third, selecting the most appropriate AI-based orchestration algorithm from a pool of candidates. This approach is intended to maximize the effectiveness of VNF allocation.

The system supports an extensive list of optimization algorithms, including Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP), Ant Colony Optimization, Greedy, Simulated Annealing, and Branch and Bound, and is designed to accommodate additional algorithms as needed. The selection of the optimal algorithm is driven by the dual objectives of minimizing response time and maximizing placement efficiency, guided by a predictive Decision Tree model trained on historical execution data.

Figure 35- Illustration of the key three steps of the AI-based meta

Following, the steps to perform meta-orchestration are detailed.

- **Select allocation strategy:** the first decision point is to determine the most appropriate allocation strategy depending on the capabilities specified in the security policies. This could involve deploying new services, reconfiguring, removing or redeploying them. The choice of action takes into account the type of service, its current state and the load of the deployed instances. After receiving a policy, the SO validates if it is feasible to perform it (checking if service is available, if there are enough resources to allocate if needed, ...). In most cases, configuration is the most appropriate solution, as takes less time and resources. Actions such as deletion, redeployment or migration are often explicit in the policy.
- **Construct candidate graph:** the candidate graph represents the possible deployment or configuration options, where the nodes represents the characteristics of the node or worker, or an instantiated software or enabler ready to be configured. Each node also has a candidate enabler, a cost associated with that enabler, and the edges weight representing connectivity. The construction of this graph provides a structured view of the orchestration options, serving as input to the orchestration algorithms, that will use it to determine the most appropriate enabler for deployment and its associated cost.
- **Select orchestration algorithm:** the final decision-making is selecting the most suitable orchestration algorithm based on the characteristic of the graph and the requirements of the policy. Currently, the SO supports MILP, Ant Colony, Greedy, Simulated Annealing, and

Branch and Bound algorithms. To choose the most suitable one, fastest response and maximum placement optimization (depending on policy requirements and infrastructure status) are considered. This information serves as input for the set of models designed to select the most suitable algorithm to use, which are designed with a specific objective, balancing speed and optimization. Once the allocation action, graph and algorithm have been determined, the meta-orchestration layer ensures that orchestration receives a specific action to perform, a set of potential candidates, and an algorithm aligned with the specific objectives.

Compared to previous versions of the Security Orchestrator, which did not include the use of meta-orchestration using AI models, this latest implementation provides more refined options for the orchestration process. Instead of relying in pre-configured options to select orchestration candidates, this new AI-based meta-orchestration provides a more fine-grain orchestration process, ensuring that more information is taken into account to select the most suitable solution for the application of a security policy, such as policy requirements, the status of the service or enabler, or the load of the deployed instances.

The orchestrator performance was evaluated in a simulated environment of 0 to 100 nodes, representing a small-to-medium data center. Each simulation uses the 5 different algorithms (MILP, Branch and Bound, Simulated Annealing, Ant Colony and Greedy), with each algorithm being executed for orchestrating a policy 5 times, and each policy being enforced in 3 different environments, and the whole process is repeated 3 times with a set of constraints from 0 to 2, for a total of 22500 executions. The evaluation measured time-related factors, specifically meta-orchestration time, decision time, and orchestration time (deployment and enforcement) across three different Management and Orchestration (MANO) approaches: OSM with Kubernetes (OSM+K8s), OSM with OpenStack VMs (OSM+VM), and standalone Kubernetes (k8s).

The results for meta-orchestration of figures show that Kubernetes-based configurations initially had higher graph-building times compared to the VM-based setup. This overhead was caused by the need to search for descriptors like Helm charts in repositories, but it was eliminated after the first operation as the descriptor was cached, significantly reducing subsequent graph-building times. As expected, graph construction time increased proportionally with the number of nodes due to growing database management complexity.

Figure 36-Time to complete meta-orchestration vs. number of nodes

Regarding decision time, as shown in next figure, the Greedy algorithm was the fastest and most stable, with its performance remaining nearly constant as the infrastructure size increased. The Branch and Bound algorithm achieved decision times that closely approximated the Greedy algorithm's performance following optimization efforts. In contrast, Ant Colony Optimization yielded the highest decision times, and Simulated Annealing's time increased steadily as nodes were added. MILP, while offering optimal solutions, scaled poorly for larger datasets

Figure 37-Time to decide the optimal set of enablers vs. number of nodes

For orchestration time, as shown in next figure, the standalone Kubernetes (k8s) configuration was the most efficient, achieving the shortest deployment times of 30 to 35 seconds due to the absence of intermediary layers. The OSM+K8s setup was next at around 40 seconds, while the

OSM+VM approach was the slowest, averaging 60 seconds for deployment due to VM-related overheads. For enforcement, standalone Kubernetes and OSM+Kubernetes also yielded the fastest times.

Figure 38-Orchestration times (deployment and enforcement) for different MANO approaches

The evaluation demonstrates that the meta-orchestration framework improves the responsiveness and scalability. By integrating AI with dynamic orchestration mechanisms, the framework enables efficient allocation of VNFs across the network continuum. As can be seen, K8s outperforms OSM when it comes to deployment and enforcement. The Security Orchestrator is able to select the most suitable approaches and algorithms depending on different factors, such as the availability of the MANO technologies (OSM+VM, OSM+k8s or k8s) in the scenario, or the requirements in the decision (MILP could be used to find optimal solutions with small datasets, while Greedy algorithms provide non-optimal solutions but they are stable and fast).

4.2. IoT bootstrapping mechanisms

The IoT bootstrapping mechanisms are described in detail in Deliverable D3.2, clause 4.2.

4.3 Trusted application onboarding

The trusted application onboarding is described in detail in Deliverable D3.2, clause 4.3.

5 ZERO TRUST AND SMART SECURITY MANAGEMENT

5.1. Trust evaluation and Trust enabler service framework

The Trust Evaluation and Trust Enabler Service Function (TESF) is designed as a standalone or collective service in the RIGOROUS architecture responsible for evaluating the trustworthiness of entities (e.g., UEs, network functions, or external application function) in a 5G/6G network. The TEF achieves this by collecting data from multiple sources, analysing abnormal behavioural patterns, and dynamically assigning trust scores to the entities involved. The TEF operates in real-time or near-real-time and interfaces with the 5G Core control plane and security management layers to evaluate behaviour and respond to trust-based violations through score-driven decision-making. Furthermore, the TEF can also assign trust score to entities in the network based on anomaly detection results from the SIEM or any similar monitoring and analyser tools. The enhanced architecture of the TEF from D3.2 is show in next Figure.

Figure 39 - Trust Evaluation and Trust Enabler Service Framework

The main functional components in the TEF can be listed as follows:

- **Monitoring Services:** Collect raw data such as logs of the Network Functions (NFs), infrastructure footprints such as CPU usage, Memory usage, network traffic metrics (such as packets received, sent and dropped from the NFs containers) as well as specified violation from the SIEM or any anomaly detectors.
- **Webhook and Processor:** Collects events and violations, validates and processes alerts from the Monitoring Services.
- **Trust Manager:** Assigns trust scores to the network entities like UEs or NFs based on anomalies and violations.

- **Trust Score Database:** Persists historical and real-time trust values.
- **REST API Interface:** Exposes trust score data to external orchestrators and controllers.

The TESH operates in three core phases:

1. **Monitoring and Data Collection:** Uses a custom telemetry system to collect metrics and logs from the 5G NFs and virtualization layer.
2. **Violation Detection and Attribution:** Parses NF logs (e.g., AMF) to identify patterns like excessive registration updates, then attributes violations to specific UEs.
3. **Trust Score Assignment:** Applies a formula to compute and update entity trust scores and publishes alerts when thresholds are violated.

5.2 Trust Algorithm:

To detect behavioural anomalies and guide trust score adjustment, TESH employs a Multimodal Autoencoder (MAE). This unsupervised deep learning model reconstructs expected behaviour patterns from normal data and flags deviations as anomalies. The overview of the process can be shown as in next figure:

Figure 40 - Process of anomaly detection using MAE and trust score assignment

i. Multimodal Data

- Modality 1 (Footprints): Telemetry Features such as CPU, memory, packet stats (per NF)
- Modality 2 (Logs Analysis): Log-Based Event Counts as Configuration updates, DNN session attempts, UPF sessions.

ii. Model Structure

- Encoders: Encode each modality separately

- Fusion Layer: Concatenates latent representations (i.e., compressed representation of data points that preserves only essential features that inform the input data's underlying structure).
- Decoder: Attempts to reconstruct the original input.

iii. Loss Function

Let the input data consist of multiple modalities:

- $x^{(1)}$: Log-encoded vector (e.g., AMF/SMF/UPF logs).
- $x^{(2)}$: Telemetry data vector (e.g., CPU, memory).
- $\hat{x}^{(1)}, \hat{x}^{(2)}$: Reconstructed versions of each modality.

The total reconstruction loss \mathcal{L}_{total} is the sum of the reconstruction errors for each modality. We typically use Mean Squared Error (MSE) for continuous data as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{total} = \mathcal{L}_{rec}^{(1)} + \mathcal{L}_{rec}^{(2)} = \|x^{(1)} - \hat{x}^{(1)}\|_2^2 + \|x^{(2)} - \hat{x}^{(2)}\|_2^2$$

If the model includes more modalities M , the generalized total loss becomes:

$$\mathcal{L}_{total} = \sum_{m=1}^M \|x^{(m)} - \hat{x}^{(m)}\|_2^2$$

iv. Anomaly Score Calculation

After training on normal data, the reconstruction error \mathcal{L} for each input sample indicates its anomaly level. We normalize it:

$$AnomalyScore = \min\left(1.0, \frac{\mathcal{L}}{\theta}\right)$$

where θ is a pre-set high threshold from training data.

v. Trust Score Assignment

Trust score of entity i , T_i is updated using:

$$T_i = T_i^{prev} - (\alpha \cdot V_i + \beta \cdot \mu_i + \gamma \cdot \max(S_i))$$

Where the following variable are:

- T_i^{prev} : Previous trust score of the entity i .
- V_i : Number of violations (e.g., config update floods).
- μ_i : Mean anomaly score for entity in a time window.
- $\max(S_i)$: Maximum anomaly score over time.
- α, β, γ : Tunable weights.

5.3 Empirical Analysis

We deployed 3 UEs using UERANSIM and registered them through Open5GS AMF. Among these, 2 UEs were configured to repeatedly send registration requests (mimicking a DoS attack) varying the severity of the attack for the 2nd and 3rd UE (more severe). Monitoring Input: Periodic snapshots of system and NF telemetry (CPU, memory, packet stats) and parsed log entries (e.g., configuration update commands, session messages). Anomaly Detection Engine: A Multimodal Autoencoder (MAE) processes telemetry and log features to learn "normal" behaviour. Spikes in reconstruction loss are interpreted as anomalies. Trust Score Engine: For each entity involved (e.g., UE IMSI, NF ID), TESP uses the anomaly output to decrease trust scores based on the frequency and severity of violations. Based on this scenario, we track the anomaly score and the corresponding trust score generation by the trust manager as in the Figure 5.3.1 and Figure 5.3.2.

Figure 41 - Anomaly Score

Figure 42 - Trust Scores

We observe that the anomaly scores over time two distinct spikes represent abnormal events (e.g., DoS-style activity) and the dashed gray line at 0.1 indicates the anomaly detection threshold. Whereas for Trust Score Evolution, the Trust scores inversely mirror the anomaly spikes, during attack periods, the trust score dips rapidly and a threshold at 70 flags entities with low reliability.

Figure 43 - UE Specific Trust Scores

As from previous figure, in the UE-specific trust score timeline plot, we observe that the IMSI001 maintains full trust (100) throughout the monitoring period, representing a well-behaved UE while the IMSI002 shows gradual trust degradation due to minor or infrequent anomalies and the IMSI003 exhibits a steep trust decline, crossing below the critical trust threshold (70), indicating potential malicious behaviour or policy violations

6 END-TO-END MULTIDOMAIN MULTI-TENANT 6G SLICING

6.1. Security Agents and Security Slice Controllers for End-to-end multi-domain slicing

In order to achieve security in network slices between different domains, security agents and slice controllers must be deployed in the scenario. Security agents are in charge of monitoring and managing the network elements, obtaining data from the devices that can be used to make security decisions, and applying security enforcements from orchestrators. Security slice controllers generate and enforce channel protection policies for network slices from the security orchestrator.

6.1.1. Orchestration of channel-protected security slices

Channel protection policies provide a way to ensure that communication between endpoints in the network is secured through the use of IPsec tunnels. As stated in previous deliverables, the Security Orchestrator might use this type of policies to mitigate different attacks to enablers in the RIGUROUS architecture, such as MITM (Man-In-The-Middle) or any other type of attack related to eavesdropping the communication through the network. The RIGUROUS architecture takes advantage of the centralized design of the Software-Defined Networking (SDN) to apply IPsec configurations directly to the enablers. The previous version of the prototype was able to create tunnels only between enablers that were in the same network and managed by the same controller. However, in this last iteration of the development, we were able to expand the architectural design and the implementation to also support the configuration of SDN nodes that are deployed in different networks and under the management of different controllers, which effectively provides a way for end-to-end communication through the network. In order to achieve this, the Security Orchestrator makes use of a set of related components that provide the functionality to create and apply the IPsec configuration, which are:

- End-to-End Security Orchestrator (E2E SO): This component provides a way to apply channel protection policies in environments with endpoints under the management of different Security Orchestrators, or even in different domains. In the RIGUROUS architecture, it's located over a set of different Security Orchestrators, managing them through the use of policies, in the same way as a Security Orchestrator configures different enablers.
- SDN Controller: The SDN Controller receives information related to the creation of a certain tunnel from the Security Orchestrator from one endpoint to another, and creates a specific configuration message for the endpoint(s) that it manages. As in End-To-End Multidomain Multi-tenant most communications involve endpoints that will be in different networks, and thus managed by different Security Orchestrators and SDN Controllers, they are prepared to create and apply IPsec policies and security associations only to SDN nodes that are under their control, but they are able also to create tunnels between nodes connected in the same network and managed under the same controller.
- SDN Node: It provides all the functionality to apply the IPsec configuration directly in the enabler. Any component in the network that uses IPsec tunnels to secure the exchange of

traffic with another component is labeled as SDN Node, and will communicate with the SDN Controller to do so.

Figure 6.1.1.1. shows flow diagram of a channel-protected policy application in a multidomain and multi-operator scenario. It is showed how the End-To-End Security Orchestrator receives a policy from either the Decision Engine or the Intent-based Security Modelling component (message 1.A or 1.B), and then processes it creating a subset of policies to apply in the correspondent Security Orchestrator in each operator (messages 2.A and 2.B). As a result, each Security Orchestrator will process the policies received from the E2E SO and will create configuration messages for the enablers (messages 3.A and 3.B), which in this case are the SDN controllers located in the corresponding domain of each operator. Then, each SDN controller will create the final configuration for the SDN node located in the domain (messages 4.A and 4.B), thus creating the IPsec tunnel between both domains and operators (message 5).

Figure 44 - Message flow for a multidomain and multi-operator channel protection scenario

6.1.2. Slice Manager

This subsection introduces the final functional prototype of the Slice Manager (SM) component within the RIGUROUS architecture. The SM is responsible for enabling End-to-End (E2E) network slicing in multi-tenant, multi-domain 5G/6G infrastructures. A key objective of the RIGUROUS project is to provide an adaptive, interoperable, and flexible E2E network slicing architecture that supports 6G deployments. The SM ensures that network slicing can serve as a mitigation technique, isolating harmful traffic from cyber-attacks in a low-priority, low-bandwidth slice while protecting legitimate user traffic, services, and the 6G infrastructure.

As outlined in deliverable D3.1, the initial SM prototype consists of three main sub-components, described as follows:

- **SM NBI (API REST):** The Slice Manager exposes a North-Bound Interface (NBI) to the UMU orchestrator through a REST API. This API is invoked when a network slice needs to be created or deleted in the data plane, or when a malicious traffic flow is assigned to an existing slice. Communication between the UMU orchestrator and SM is facilitated using JSON messages.
- **E2E Slice Engine:** The E2E Slice Engine is responsible for managing the network slices deployed in the data plane. It interacts with the orchestrator to provide slice capabilities. The engine relies on topological data from the Topology Inventory Agent (TIA), which enables the SM to make informed decisions on where to deploy slices across the network. The Slice Engine sends technology-agnostic slice definitions to Security Control Agents (SCAs) deployed throughout the infrastructure, specifying actions such as slice creation, deletion, or attaching traffic to a slice.
- **Security Control Agent (SCA):** The SCA functions as the South-Bound Interface of the SM. Deployed on infrastructure nodes, the SCA provides programmability for various technologies and network interfaces within the data plane, specifically for network slice lifecycle management. It abstracts the complexity of the network for the SM and translates the technology-agnostic slice definitions from the E2E Slice Engine into technology-specific actions, ensuring that slice operations (creation, deletion, or attachment) are executed correctly within the data plane.

The following results are obtained from the experiments and testbed scenarios depicted in section 6.2 of D4.3. This testbed used to evaluate the WP3 and WP4 components (NSFM, TIA, SMPS, SM and NSP) developed by UWS/Aston. Each results section referring to these components will link back to this shared experimental setup. The test scenarios emulate a 5G/6G network infrastructure using the CORE emulator, which employs Linux network namespaces to simulate network elements such as UEs, Edge servers, and gNodeBs. An extension developed by UWS/Aston automates topology creation, experiment execution, and results storage in a SQL database. All tests were performed on a high-performance physical server running Ubuntu 20.04 LTS with kernel 5.15.0, featuring a 56-core Intel Xeon E5-2660 v4 CPU and 128 GB of DDR4 RAM.

The experiments simulate a DDoS attack launched by a botnet of infected UEs targeting a victim in a separate domain, with traffic traversing a shared infrastructure. The mitigation strategy involves creating a dedicated E2E network slice for each affected UE, with bandwidth limited to 1 Kbps. The NSFM detects the malicious flows, the TIA supplies topological data, and the SMPS formulates the mitigation plan. Mitigation is then coordinated by the SO and SM, and enforced by the NSP in the

data plane. The attack traffic consists of fixed-rate UDP floods at 10 Mbps per infected UE. The scenarios used in the experiments vary in topology: with one Edge server, there are 8, 16, or 32 UEs; with two Edge servers, 16, 32, or 64 UEs; and with four Edge servers, 32, 64, or 128 UEs.

Figure 45 - Average time consumed by the SM to create an intention to mitigate the cyber threats. shows the average time required by the SM to create an intention for mitigating detected attacks, in collaboration with the SO. The SM is responsible for translating the high-level, user-friendly intention into a set of specific technological operations that the orchestration layer can act upon. The analysis spans the three usual configurations (1, 2, and 4 Edges), shown left to right in the figure.

Across all scenarios, the time to create an intention remains consistently below 1 second, indicating that the SM component performs this task with minimal delay. This suggests that the translation from abstract policy to concrete technological steps is lightweight and efficient, regardless of the number of UEs or the complexity of the scenario.

Nonetheless, the plots reveal a small upward trend as the topology becomes more complex and the number of UEs increases, particularly moving from 1 Edge to 2 Edge configurations. Interestingly, a reduction in time is observed in the 128 UE scenario. This may be attributed to a degradation in the overall performance of the 5G/6G network emulation at high load, potentially causing fewer effective flows or interactions to process.

Figure 45 - Average time consumed by the SM to create an intention to mitigate the cyber threats.

6.1.3. Network Self-Protection

This subsection introduces the first functional prototype of the Network Self Protection (NSP), a software-based network slicing enabler designed for 5G/6G multi-tenant networks deployed in the Data Plane (DP). The following sections provide technical details about its design, architectural sub-components, functionalities, implementation, and preliminary empirical results.

The NSP component is designed to enhance data plane programmability, offering fine-grained control over network traffic in virtualized environments, specifically within the Edge and Core segments of 5G/6G multi-tenant infrastructures. The primary goal of the NSP is to provide a novel mechanism for cyber-attack mitigation, ensuring its effectiveness in safeguarding the infrastructure from potential threats.

The NSP aims to deliver network slicing capabilities as a mitigation strategy against cyber-attacks within segments that host software-based Virtual Network Functions (VNFs). More precisely, it targets the software data path in the Edge and Core segments, which interconnects the VNFs to the physical network. After conducting a comparative analysis of existing Software Data Path solutions, such as eXpress Data Path (XDP), Data Plane Development Kit (DPDK), and Open vSwitch (OVS), OVS was selected as the baseline for the NSP implementation. The key reasons for this decision are as follows:

- OVS is a widely deployed software switch in virtualized and Software-Defined Networking (SDN) environments, where it has become the de-facto standard.
- OVS is an open-source SDN software switch, actively developed and supported by a large and vibrant developer community.
- It offers a North-Bound Interface (NBI) based on OpenFlow (OF), which can be extended to enable enhanced programmability in the data plane.
- OVS is widely adopted by frameworks and cloud management tools such as OpenStack.
- It has demonstrated proven efficiency, robust performance, and reliability in production environments.

This makes OVS an ideal foundation for the NSP, ensuring it can meet the requirements of 5G/6G infrastructures while enabling effective cyber-attack mitigation.

6.1.3.1. EMPIRICAL EVALUATION AND VALIDATION

The following results are obtained from the experiments and testbed scenarios depicted in section 6.2 of D4.3.

Next figure presents the total number of OpenFlow (OF) rules enforced by the NSP component in each of the experimental scenarios. These rules, automatically applied at the end of the self-protection loop, represent the final mitigation actions deployed in the system. In addition to enforcement, the NSP also monitors these rules periodically to ensure their effectiveness over time. The bar plots reflect results across the three edge configurations: 1, 2, and 4 Edges.

Overall, the number of enforced OF rules tends to increase with the scale and complexity of the topology, i.e., with a higher number of UEs and more Edge servers. This aligns with expectations, as a more distributed infrastructure and a greater number of attack flows require more mitigation actions, which in turn translates to a higher number of flow rules.

However, there are notable exceptions. For instance, with 16 UEs, the 2 Edge configuration shows a slight reduction in rules compared to the 1 Edge case. Similarly, for 32 UEs, the number of rules drops when moving from 2 to 4 Edges (from 131.3 to 100.7 on average). These anomalies may be attributed to the growing complexity of the network, which could affect the efficiency of the mitigation process. Additionally, errors or missing data propagated from earlier stages of the self-protection loop, such as detection (NSFM), planning (SMPS), and orchestration (SM/SO), may result in incomplete or suboptimal enforcement. The sharp drop to 47.7 average rules for 128 UEs in the 4 Edge scenario underscores the strain imposed by high-scale emulation, likely reflecting systemic instability and resource exhaustion during mitigation.

Figure 46 - Number of handled OFnetwork slicing rules by the NSP simultaneously

Figure 46 represents the average time required by the NSP component to create a network slice within the datapath using OVS (Open vSwitch) technology. The scenarios are organized by Edge configuration: 1, 2, and 4 Edge setups, corresponding to increasing levels of network distribution and scale.

The overall time consumed to create slices remains relatively stable across most cases. For example, in the 2 Edge configuration, even as the number of UEs increases, the average time stays within a narrow range of 10.7 to 13.1 seconds. This consistency suggests that the slice creation mechanism remains efficient and scalable under moderate system load and topology complexity. However, in the 4 Edge configuration, a rise in time is observed for the scenario with 128 UEs. This increase is consistent with other performance degradations seen in earlier figures and can be attributed to the substantial growth in topological complexity and the resource limitations of the emulated environment. Despite this, the system maintains a sub-20-second response time for each slice creation, which is a notable achievement.

The reason why the time consumed for 32 UEs from scenarios of 1 to 4 edges lowers, as well as for 64 UEs, is because of the distribution of the NSP along the different Edge servers, which balances the load of OVS rules that need to be applied by a single NSP. It demonstrates the feasibility of deploying reactive mitigation in real-time within self-protection loops, even under high-stress, large-scale network conditions.

Figure 47 - Average time consumed by the NSP in the enforcement of the Creation of the network slice.

Next figure shows the average time required by the NSP component to associate a detected malicious network flow with its corresponding newly created network slice. This step, orchestrated by the SO in collaboration with the SM, represents a key part of the mitigation process in the self-protection loop. The plots follow the same structure as previous figures, moving from 1 to 4 Edge configurations.

Interestingly, the time consumed for this association is generally higher than the time needed to create the slice itself. For instance, in the 1 Edge configuration with 8 UEs, the NSP takes approximately 17.2 seconds to complete the association. A more striking trend emerges when comparing different Edge configurations under similar UE loads. At 16 UEs, the time drops from 41.6 seconds in the 1 Edge setup to only 8.2 seconds in the 2 Edge scenario. This dramatic reduction highlights the positive impact of distributing workloads across multiple Edge servers.

The same pattern is observed for 32 UEs, where the time for association drops consistently across configurations: from 59.5 seconds (1 Edge), to 52.8 seconds (2 Edges), and down to 32.8 seconds (4 Edges). These results clearly illustrate the performance benefits of Edge-distributed deployment. Distributing the NSP component and spreading the network load allows the system to respond more efficiently and maintain lower mitigation times, even as the network complexity and number of malicious flows increase.

Figure 48 - Average time consumed by the NSP in the association of the malicious flow to the network slice.

The analysis of the NSP component across the last three figures highlights its critical role and overall effectiveness in the self-protection loop, particularly under increasing network stress and complexity. First, the total number of OpenFlow rules handled by the NSP scales with the number of UEs and Edges, although some degradation is observed in larger, more complex scenarios, likely due to cascading issues from earlier stages and resource constraints in the emulated environment. Secondly, the time required by the NSP to create network slices remains relatively stable across scenarios, generally staying under 20 seconds, which is a significant achievement considering the dynamic and large-scale topologies involved. Lastly, while associating malicious flows to network slices is a more time-consuming operation, the results clearly show that distributing the NSP workload across multiple Edge servers leads to significantly reduced response times and more stable behaviour. Together, these findings demonstrate the resilience and scalability of the NSP under increasing demands, while also demonstrates the value of system distribution in complex 5G/6G network environments.

7 WP3 ENABLERS SHOWCASING

This section has been added to the document to address the comments from the internal review of the project. It describes specific complex and real scenario involving the Security Orchestrator and its integration with other RIGOUROUS assets developed in WP3 such as the Slice Manager, Trust Manager, Onboarding Tools, etc. where we test real world use-cases to showcase the capabilities of the RIGOUROUS architecture in terms of 6G security as well as different capabilities of the AI integrated Security Orchestrator to apply different kind of countermeasures against attacks.

7.1 Use case description

use case based on ORO, insider attacker detected by SIEM and mitigation done by enforcing filtering, slicing and IDS policies through the orchestrator, the trust manager recomputes trust scores based on the alerts. Onboarding tools are reconfigured.

sequence diagram

Figure 49- Sequence diagram of the different components of the RIGOUROUS architecture communicating in the use case for the anomaly detection

Figure 50- Sequence diagram of the RIGOUROUS components applying the mitigation actions for the use case.

7.2 WP3 ASSETS INVOLVED

7.2.1 Security Orchestration

The Security Orchestrator (Section 4.1.1) is one of the critical parts in the RIGOROUS architecture, and plays a fundamental role in the application of the security policies and the restoration of services after anomalies or attacks occur. In this scenario, it will be in charge of the orchestration and application of three different countermeasures after an intruder gains access to the control plane: an IDS policy, to reconfigure the intrusion detection after the attacker tries to hide their acts; a slicing policy to mitigate the bandwidth degradation the intruder made after altering the 5G Core and restore it to its previous state; and a filtering policy to stop the communication from the attacker. As a result, the attack will be mitigated and the onboarding services will be reconfigured, effectively restoring the state of the architecture after the attack.

After the Decision Engine receives the intrusion alert and obtains information about the attacked assets (through trust scores from the TESP component), it decides which policies to apply in each situation and sends them to the Security Orchestrator. For this use case, three policies will be used, as stated before. The Decision Engine will send them to the Security Orchestrator, one at a time (in no particular order), and the SO will start processing them. That implies: checking the correctness of the policy within the MSPL format; ensuring that the new policy does not create a conflict with the previously applied policies; translating the policy into a configuration message for the corresponding enabler; and sending the message through the appropriate driver.

The orchestration process is also a relevant part of the policy deployment. It starts by selecting the most suitable orchestration strategy based on real-time policies and infrastructure constraints; then constructing a deployment graph of feasible configuration options; and finally by selecting the most appropriate AI-based orchestration algorithm from a pool of candidates. This approach is intended to maximize the effectiveness of VNF allocation.

7.2.2 Slicing

The SM (Section 6.1.2) plays a central role in the mitigation of a targeted cyber attack within the ORO 5G testbed. In this scenario, an intruder breaches the control plane and maliciously alters the 5G Next Generation Core (NGC) profile of a specific Universal Integrated Circuit Card (UICC), leading to a significant Quality of Service (QoS) degradation, with bandwidth dropping from 200 Mbps to just 1 Mbps. To counter this, the SM has been extended to interface with the Nokia Unified Data Repository (UDR) API, enabling direct access to the affected subscriber profiles and their configurations.

Once the SO (Section 4.1) detects the anomaly and delegates mitigation to the SM, the SM initiates a recovery process by translating the intent-based restoration command into a compatible Nokia UDR API request. It inspects the affected 5G NGC profile, verifies the degraded QoS parameters, and checks whether the UICC is still attached to the network. Upon validation, the SM issues a request to the Nokia UDR API to reconfigure the profile and restore the original QoS settings. This action completes the automated self-protection loop. A final confirmation is

sent to the SO, reporting the successful restoration of the 5G NGC profile and the resolution of the attack.

Table 3 - Resolution of the mitigation times for SM and Nokia UDR to restore the affected QoS of the 5G NGC profile from 1 to 200 Mbps of bandwidth

Test Case	UICC ID	Degraded Bandwidth (Mbps)	Restored Bandwidth (Mbps)	SM Reaction Time (s)	Nokia UDR Restoration Time (s)	Total Resolution Time (s)
TC-1	0xabcdef	1	200	0.6	14.1	14.7
TC-2	0xabcdef	1	200	0.8	6.6	7.4
TC-3	0xabcdef	1	200	0.6	12.8	13.4
TC-4	0xabcdef	1	200	0.7	13.2	13.9
TC-5	0xabcdef	1	200	1.1	21.1	22.2

Previous table presents the resolution times measured during the mitigation of a cyber attack that degraded the 5G NGC profile of a UICC from 200 Mbps to 1 Mbps. In all test cases, the SM successfully reacted to the SO's mitigation instruction, with reaction times ranging between 0.6 and 1.1 seconds. These values reflect the time taken by the SM to process the intent-based instruction, validate the affected 5G NGC profile, and issue a reconfiguration request via the UDR API. This consistent responsiveness confirms the SM's capability to promptly initiate the restoration process upon detection of a QoS degradation.

The Nokia UDR Restoration Time, which reflects the time required for the profile update to take effect after the SM's request, varies across test cases from 6.6 to 21.1 seconds. The Total Resolution Time, combining both the SM reaction and the UDR processing, ranges between 7.4 and 22.2 seconds. This variation is likely influenced by UDR processing load or underlying network conditions at the time of the experiment. Despite this, all test cases demonstrate a successful restoration of the original QoS parameters, confirming the effectiveness and reliability of the integrated self-protection mechanism. These results validate the ability of the SM component to autonomously close the mitigation loop and restore service continuity in a timely manner.

7.2.3 Filtering

In the context of automated mitigation within the RIGOUROUS infrastructure, a filtering (section 3.1.4) enabler has been developed to block malicious traffic and reinforce service availability. In this scenario, the system identifies a cyber attack originating from a known IP address attempting to overwhelm key network components. To counter this, a dynamic filtering mechanism based on VyOS is triggered to drop traffic from the attacker in real time.

The AID notifies the TRA, which is responsible for generating a mitigation policy. The TRA encodes the intent to block the attacker's IP address and communicates it to the Security Orchestrator, which manages the application. The orchestrator invokes the filtering enabler, triggering the translation of the policy into a VyOS firewall rule configuration.

The enabler includes a translator module that converts the high-level policy into a JSON structure that specifies the drop rule for the source IP address. This structure adheres to the VyOS configuration schema and is validated before being sent via a curl POST request to the VyOS API endpoint. VyOS runs as a container within a Kubernetes environment, allowing for on-demand configuration and rapid rule deployment.

7.2.4 IDS reconfiguration

As part of the mitigation strategy defined in this use case, the RIGOUROUS architecture integrates a reconfiguration mechanism for the IDS (section 3.1.7) component to maintain visibility and adapt its detection capability in response to evolving attack behaviour. The IDS used in this scenario is Snort, an open source intrusion detection engine capable of inspecting rule-based traffic.

In this use case, after the insider attacker compromises the control plane and attempts to modify critical elements of the 5G slicing infrastructure, the IDS identifies suspicious behaviour and triggers an alert. The Security Orchestrator, upon receiving the alert, initiates a policy-based reconfiguration of the deployed Snort IDS instance to improve its detection capabilities.

This reconfiguration consists of dynamically modifying the Snort rule set to focus on the observed tactics of the attacker. These updates can include:

- Adding new Snort rules targeting specific protocol or affected port ranges.
- Increasing the inspection depth for affected interfaces.
- Enabling detection rules related to internal behaviour or control plane manipulation.

The orchestrator translates the received MSPL policy into a rule set update and a Snort-compatible configuration payload. This payload is then sent over a secure connection to the Snort host/container, where it is applied without service interruption, taking advantage of Snort's ability to reload updated rule sets on the fly.

7.2.5 Trust Management

The Trust Manager aka the TESH described in the section 5.1 has the capabilities to handle alerts from the SIEM or SAE (of the RIGOUROUS platform) in order to analyze the type of anomaly and assign appropriate trust score to the sources of the attacker in real time or near real time granularities. In the following scenario, the malicious insider (who has access privilege to the ORO B5GS through a Bastion Station) changes the configuration of the slice in order to effect the QoS for a B2B customer. Here the mitigation action is followed by the interaction with the SAE (SIEM)-TRA-AID-SO-SM and ultimately the slice is reconfigured to its original configurations. The role of the TESH in this scenario is to assign trust score to the source of the attacker from the alerts received from the SAE or SIEM in order to maintain a persistent intention of the source (which may be the attacker) through trust score assignment or trigger the AID when the trust score falls below a certain pre-defined trust score (in case of repeated attempts of attack) as shown in the next

figure, We set the parameters of alpha, beta and gamma as described in the section 5.1.1 as 1, 10 and 20 whereas the trust threshold to 30 and trust is calculated based on the equation defined in section 5.2.

<pre>Response JSON: { "status": "processed", "results": [{ "source_ip": "172.28.22.186", "trust_before": 100.0, "trust_after": 80.0, "deduction": 20.0, "alert_triggered": false }] }</pre>	<pre>Response JSON: { "status": "processed", "results": [{ "source_ip": "172.28.22.186", "trust_before": 40.0, "trust_after": 20.0, "deduction": 20.0, "alert_triggered": true }] }</pre>
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Figure 51 Corresponding Trust scores of the Attacker for single attempted attack (left) and multiple attempted attacks (right).

It can be observed that the attacker IP after the attempted slice re-configuration changes has been assigned lower trust score of 80 but the alert to the AID has not been triggered as to the trust score does not fall below the threshold. While on repetition of the attack, when the IP is assigned a trust score below 30, the alert is triggered to the AID as described in D4.3 where the mitigation or remediation action is decided as a MSPL policy to inform the Security Orchestrator (to remove the entity from the network, quarantine or drop packets from the source of the attack).

7.2.6 Onboarding

The OT (section 3.3) plays a crucial role in the incident response, allowing for a quick reconfiguration of the service so that decoys (i.e., replicas with different configuration) can be deployed specifically to the attacker(s). This approach permits gathering intelligence on the attacker's tactics, techniques, and procedures as well as (potentially) understanding the objectives and motivations that lead to the attack. The operational results (i.e., overheads and times) that pertain to the OT are the same as in the evaluation under regular operation, the crucial factor that differs from a regular onboarding operation is the added filtering of the attackers and enforcement of the redirection action (instead of a simple DROP). This crucial difference is approached in section 7.2.3.

8 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this deliverable provides the final findings of the WP3 solutions aimed at enhancing security and trust in multi-domain 6G networks. The key contributions are as follows:

- Human-Centric Security, Privacy Modeling, and Onboarding: The development of detailed security and privacy models, user-friendly DevSecOps tools, and robust onboarding processes to ensure the security and privacy of network applications. Additionally, Federated Learning frameworks and enhanced policy translation tools have been integrated to strengthen the RIGOROUS security architecture.
- AI-Driven Cross-Domain Security and Privacy Orchestration in the IoT-Edge-Cloud Continuum: AI-powered security orchestration is being deployed to enable dynamic, adaptive security management across the IoT, RAN, edge, core, and cloud domains. The achieved results shows promising meta-orchestration employing different AI algorithms.
- Zero Trust and Smart Security Management: The development of a standalone Trust Evaluation and Trust Enabler Service Framework (TESF) is underway, allowing for trust score assignment based on violation data and statistics collected from network entities. This framework supports proactive risk management and dynamic threat responses, using AI-driven decision-making for better threat mitigation.
- End-to-End Multidomain Multi-Tenant 6G Slicing: Security agents and slice controllers are deployed to ensure secure network slices across multiple domains. These components are essential for monitoring, managing, and enforcing security policies, thereby safeguarding the integrity and security of multi-domain network slices. The autonomic, model-driven multi-domain and multi-operator channel protection with IPSEC integrated in the orchestrator guarantees the confidentiality in B5G networks.

7 LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Table 5 List of abbreviations and acronyms.

Abbreviation	Explanation/ Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
HTTP/HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol/Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
UML	Unified Modeling Language
MSPL	Medium-level Security Policy Language
IPsec	Internet Protocol Security
SDN	Software Defined Networks
OpenC2	Open Command and Control

FL	Federated Learning
IP	Internet Protocol Address
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
SQA	Software Quality Assurance
TRA	Threat Risk Assessor
UI	User Interface
OSS	Operations Support System
NSaaS	Network Slices as a Service
NFVO	Network Functions Virtualization Orchestrator
VNF	Virtual Network Function
TMF	Tele Management Forum
NS	Network Service
MANO	Management and Orchestration
SCUI	Service Composition UI
PUI	Human Controllable Privacy
NFV	Network Functions Virtualization
NSDs	Network Service Descriptor
AOUI	Application Onboarding UI
PCF	Policy Control Function
SSLAs	Security Service Level Agreement
SPs	Security Policies
HSPL-OP	High-level Technology-Agnostic Policy Models
SO	Security Orchestrator
MTD	Moving Target Defense
SMUI	Security Formal Modeling
ReMUI	Response-Mitigation Policies
RM	Response-Mitigation
DSC	Dynamic Service Composer

VC	Verifiable Credentials
PDL	Permissioned Distributed Ledger
PLMN	Public Land Mobile Network
NPN	Non-Public Networks
UE	User Equipment
DID	Decentralized IDentifier
L-RMS	Ledger Role-Based Registration Management Service
DPRS	DID Operational participants registry service
DTMF	Dual Tone Multi-Frequency
DRS	DID Resolver service
DDRS	DID Document Registry service
VDRS	VC Data Registry service
DVMS	DID verification management service
NAI	Network Access Identifier
NAS	Non-Access Stratum
AMF	Access and Mobility Management Function
TSP	Trusted Service Provider
IDP	Identification Service Provider
MAC	Medium Access Control
UDM	Unified Data Management
UDR	Unified Data Repository
SUPI	Subscription Permanent Identifier
IMSI	International Mobile Subscription Identity
AUSF	Authentication Server Function
OAI	Onboard Assistance Information
IoT	Internet of Things
RAN	Radio Access Network
E2E	End-to-End

HSPL-OP	High-level Security Policy Language Orchestration Policy
ISM	Intent-based Security Management
MSPL-OP	Medium-level Security Policy Language Orchestration Policies
D2D	Device-to-Device
ABC	Attribute Based Credentials
UEPK	UE Public Key
DCS	Default Credential Server
AAA	Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting
SBI	Service Based Interface
EAP	Extensible Authentication Protocol
MSK	Master Session Key
SMC	Security Mode Command
IPsec	Internet Protocol Security
SEAF	SEcurity Anchor Function
NEF	Network Exposure Function
5G-GUTI	5G- Globally Unique Temporary UE Identity
URSP	UE Route Selection Policy
CAS	Certified Application Server
TESF	Trust Evaluation and Trust Enabler service
PDU	Packet Data Unit
5G SA	5G Standalone
gNB	gNodeB
SDN	Software Defined Networks
SPD	Security Policy Database
SAD	Security Association Database
SA	Security associations
NSP	Network Services Platform
DP	Data Plane

COTS	Commercial Off-The-Shelf
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
OF	Open Flow
ONF	Open Networking Foundation
QoS	Quality of Service
XDP	eXpress Data Path
DPDK	Data Plane Development Kit
NBI	North-Bound Interface
SLA	Service Level Agreement

10 LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE 1 - SECURITY POLICY MODELS DEFINITION IN SYSTEM MODEL SCHEMA	10
FIGURE 2 - SPD DEFINITION FOR SECURITY POLICY IN SYSTEM MODEL SCHEMA	11
FIGURE 3 - SAD DEFINITION FOR SECURITY POLICY IN SYSTEM MODEL SCHEMA	11
FIGURE 4 - COMMANDCONTROLRULEACTION DEFINITION FOR COMMAND AND CONTROL IN SYSTEM MODEL SCHEMA.....	12
FIGURE 5 - COMMANDCONTROLACTIONTYPE DEFINITION FOR COMMAND AND CONTROL IN SYSTEM MODEL SCHEMA.....	12
FIGURE 6 - CAMERARULEPARAMETERS DEFINITION FOR COMMAND AND CONTROL IN SYSTEM MODEL SCHEMA	12
FIGURE 7 - FILTERFLCONFIGURATIONCONDITION DEFINITION FOR FEDERATED LEARNING IN SYSTEM MODEL SCHEMA.....	13
FIGURE 8 - AGGREGATORPARAMETERS DEFINITION FOR FEDERATED LEARNING IN SYSTEM MODEL SCHEMA	14
FIGURE 9 - LEARNINGPARAMETERS DEFINITION FOR FEDERATED LEARNING IN SYSTEM MODEL SCHEMA	14
FIGURE 10 - LIFECYCLE OF THE FILTERING POLICY IN THE ORCHESTRATOR	15
FIGURE 11- FIREWALLRULEACTION DEFINITION FOR VYOS FIREWALL IN SYSTEM MODEL SCHEMA	16
FIGURE 12 - FIREWALLACTIONTYPE DEFINITION FOR VYOS FIREWALL IN SYSTEM MODEL SCHEMA	16
FIGURE 13 - RULEPARAMETERS DEFINITION FOR VYOS FIREWALL IN SYSTEM MODEL SCHEMA	17
FIGURE 14 - SIEM RULE EXAMPLE DEFINITION	17
FIGURE 15- NETWORK SLICING ACTION TYPE.....	18
FIGURE 16- QOS CONDITION	18
FIGURE 17- SLICING CONDITION.....	18
FIGURE 18NETWORK SLICING ACTION	19
FIGURE 19-PACKET FILTERING CONDITION EXAMPLE	19
FIGURE 20- NETWORK SLICING CONDITION PARAMETERS.....	19
FIGURE 21 - MONITORING POLICY ACTION EXAMPLE.....	20
FIGURE 22 - PACKET FILTERING CONDITION FOR IDS POLICY	20
FIGURE 23 - ORCHESTRATION POLICY EXAMPLE	21
FIGURE 24- PRIORITY IN POLICIES DURING ORCHESTRATION.....	21
FIGURE 25 - PRIVGUIDE DEPLOYMENT DIAGRAM.....	23
FIGURE 26 - PRIVGUIDE WEB INTERFACE.	24
FIGURE 27 - COMPONENTS COMPRISING THE ONBOARDING TOOLS AND THEIR INTERACTION.....	27
FIGURE 28 - RISK SPECIFICATION.	28
FIGURE 29 - RIGOUROUS SERVICE CATALOGUE WITH DIFFERENT TAGS RELATED TO PRIVACY AWARENESS.....	29
FIGURE 30 - EXAMPLE OF A TM FORUM SERVICE SPECIFICATION CHARACTERISTIC FOR DECLARING THE PORT OF A SERVICE.....	29
FIGURE 31 - TM FORUM SERVICE SPECIFICATION CHARACTERISTIC FOR MUTATING THE PORT OF A SERVICE.	31

FIGURE 32 - NMTD POLICY IN THE TM FORUM SERVICE SPECIFICATION FORMAT FOR ROTATION OF ALL SUPPORTED ATTRIBUTES.....	31
FIGURE 33 - SECURITY ORCHESTRATOR ARCHITECTURE DIAGRAM.....	34
FIGURE 34 - END-TO-END SECURITY ORCHESTRATOR ARCHITECTURE DIAGRAM.....	37
FIGURE 35- ILLUSTRATION OF THE KEY THREE STEPS OF THE AI-BASED META.....	38
FIGURE 36-TIME TO COMPLETE META-ORCHESTRATION VS. NUMBER OF NODES.....	40
FIGURE 37 -TIME TO DECIDE THE OPTIMAL SET OF ENABLERS VS. NUMBER OF NODES.....	40
FIGURE 38-ORCHESTRATION TIMES (DEPLOYMENT AND ENFORCEMENT) FOR DIFFERENT MANO APPROACHES.....	41
FIGURE 39 - TRUST EVALUATION AND TRUST ENABLER SERVICE FRAMEWORK.....	42
FIGURE 40 - PROCESS OF ANOMALY DETECTION USING MAE AND TRUST SCORE ASSIGNMENT....	43
FIGURE 41 - ANOMALY SCORE.....	45
FIGURE 42 - TRUST SCORES.....	45
FIGURE 43 - UE SPECIFIC TRUST SCORES.....	46
FIGURE 44 - MESSAGE FLOW FOR A MULTIDOMAIN AND MULTI-OPERATOR CHANNEL PROTECTION SCENARIO.....	48
FIGURE 45 - AVERAGE TIME CONSUMED BY THE SM TO CREATE AN INTENTION TO MITIGATE THE CYBER THREATS.....	50
FIGURE 46 - NUMBER OF HANDLED OFNETWORK SLICING RULES BY THE NSP SIMULTANEOUSLY.....	52
FIGURE 47 - AVERAGE TIME CONSUMED BY THE NSP IN THE ENFORCEMENT OF THE CREATION OF THE NETWORK SLICE.....	52
FIGURE 48 - AVERAGE TIME CONSUMED BY THE NSP IN THE ASSOCIATION OF THE MALICIOUS FLOW TO THE NETWORK SLICE.....	53
FIGURE 49- SEQUENCE DIAGRAM OF THE DIFFERENT COMPONENTS OF THE RIGOUROUS ARCHITECTURE COMMUNICATING IN THE USE CASE FOR THE ANOMALY DETECTION.....	55
FIGURE 50- SEQUENCE DIAGRAM OF THE RIGOUROUS COMPONENTS APPLYING THE MITIGATION ACTIONS FOR THE USE CASE.....	56
FIGURE 51CORRESPONDING TRUST SCORES OF THE ATTACKER FOR SINGLE ATTEMPTED ATTACK (LEFT) AND MULTIPLE ATTEMPTED ATTACKS (RIGHT).	60

11 LIST OF TABLES

TABLE 1 - MEDIAN AND AVERAGE EXECUTION TIME FOR THE TOOL AT 10000 EXECUTIONS.....	25
TABLE 2 - MEDIAN AND AVERAGE MEMORY USAGE FOR THE TOOL AT 10000 EXECUTIONS.	25
TABLE 3 - RESOLUTION OF THE MITIGATION TIMES FOR SM AND NOKIA UDR TO RESTORE THE AFFECTED QOS OF THE 5G NGC PROFILE FROM 1 TO 200 MBPS OF BANDWIDTH.....	58

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